

ST CLEMENTS UNIVERSITY

Department of Psychology

**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ADOLESCENTS'
ATTITUDES TOWARDS WOMEN'S POLITICAL
REPRESENTATION IN TURKEY AND SOCIAL PHOBIA IN
THE CONTEXT OF GENDER**

License Thesis

Nazmiye ESKİ

Advisor

Prof. Dr. Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER

Ankara – 2024

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DECLARATION

I declare that the rules of scientific ethics were followed in the preparation of this thesis, that if the works of others were used, they were cited in accordance with scientific norms, that there was no distortion of the data used, and that no part of the thesis was presented as another thesis at this university or any other university.

Nazmiye ESKİ

03/02/2024

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TO THE DIRECTORATE OF THE INSTITUTE OF SOCIAL SCIENCES

Nazmiye ESKİ's thesis titled "Examination of the Relationship Between Adolescents' Attitudes towards Political Representations of Women in Turkey in the Context of Gender and Social Anxiety" was accepted by our jury as an undergraduate thesis in the Department of Psychology, Department of Psychology.

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Dedicated to my family for their love, support and so much more ...

SUMMARY

“Women internalize the 'female images' created by the dominant culture. they move towards change, they have to struggle not only with external pressures and obstacles, but also with these dominant cultural definitions that they carry within themselves.”
(Berktaş, 2016: 18).

The aim of this research is to examine the relationship between social phobia and adolescents' attitudes towards political representation of women in Turkey in the context of gender. This study was designed according to the parallel design type that converges from mixed research methods, and the population of the research consists of 12th grade students studying in public schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in Ankara province, Çankaya, Sincan and Etimesgut districts in the 2023-2024 academic year. As a sample, 17-year-old high school senior students were used using the convenience sampling method, which is one of the non-probability sampling methods. As data collection sources in the study, Socio -demographic Data Form, Full and Semi-Structured Interview Form were developed by the researcher, and Gender Perception Scale and Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale were used. Collected data; It was analyzed using SPSS 25 Statistics program. For the qualitative part of the research, the nested multiple case design was chosen from the case study designs , and the easily accessible sampling method, one of the purposeful sampling methods, was preferred as the sample. As for the study group, a total of 12 students, 1 girl and 1 boy each, studying in 3 different high schools (Vocational-Science-Imam Hatip High School) within the framework of volunteering with the maximum diversity sampling method, were targeted and the targeted number was reached. Research: As a data collection technique, face-to-face and online (zoom) interviews were held and these interviews were recorded. The data obtained from the Qualitative Data analyzes were first transferred to the computer environment by transcription, then classified by an expert in the field with the NVIVO 11 Package program, and then the descriptive analysis process was applied. The results were subjected to Kappa analysis and qualitative data analyzes were interpreted. According to the results obtained in the research, it was determined that there was a positive relationship between social awareness and gender perception.

Key Words: Social Anxiety (Social Phobia), Political Tendency in Adolescents, Political Tendency in Women in Turkey, Gender, Political Representation of Women

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ABBREVIATIONS

EU	:	European Union
APB	:	American Psychiatric Association
CBT	:	Cognitive Behavioral Therapy
UN	:	United Nations
SIS	:	State Institute of Statistics
DSM	:	The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5, Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5
E-GBBT	:	Cognitive Behavioral Group Therapy for Adolescents
ICD	:	International Classification of Diseases
ISE High School	:	Istanbul Stock Exchange High School
KA-DER	:	Association for Support and Education of Female Candidates
LSKÖ	:	Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale
MEB	:	Ministry of National Education
MTAL	:	Vocational and Technical High School
ÖF	:	Specific Phobia

SAD	:	Social Anxiety Disorder
SET	:	Social Effectiveness Method
SF	:	Social Phobia
SPSS	:	Statistical Package For Social Sciences
Assembly of Turkey	:	Grand National Assembly of Turkey
TCRT	:	Gender Roles Attitude Scale
UNESCO	:	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNIFEM	:	United Nations Development Fund for Women
Vd	:	And others
GAD	:	Generalized Anxiety Disorder

DEFINITIONS AND CONCEPTS

Gender : The biological characteristics of men and women are different from birth. can be defined as being . (Lindsey , 2016)

Adolescent : ' 1. Being in a reproductive position, masculine, mentally retarded' (TDK)

"2. "He is single, not married yet." (TDK)

Role : The duty of a person or thing in a job.

Social Anxiety Disorder (Social Phobia-Social Anxiety Disorder): Showing an avoidant attitude in activities such as eating in social areas, meeting new people, presenting, showing an avoidant attitude in communicating with authority figures, in situations where performance is required, worrying about being judged in representing oneself and the society and in events. It is defined as the state of experiencing anxiety with anxiety. (Bandelow , Wedekind , 2014; Ballenger , Davidson, Lecrubier et al., 1998)

Politics: Politics in society political authority , poweremergeremoval , operation , operation _
_inspection and necessarywhen seen _Oneotherwise _ _can be changed _ _topicsvery wide
including _comprehensive and complex _ _a structured socialis a fact .

Political Participation: Political participationif , thisperiodinside
,necessaryindividualbothsocietyvarious _ _by segmentsemergeplacedthought , attitude , situation
and mutual _ _effectwithreactionof your movementsthe wholeIt covers .

Gender: In the context of gender, the definition of women and men by the values and judgments
of the society they live in can be expressed as a kind of identity definition determined by the
society. (Serdaroğlu, 2010)

Gender Roles: Roles are not biologically attributed to humans, but are later expected,
determined and assumed by society.

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PREFACE

Anxiety disorders are among the most common psychological disorders today, with a rate of 18.1% . The disorder is divided into diagnostic and statistical sections. According to DSM 5 (Manual of Mental Disorders 5) and ICD-10 (International Classification of Diseases), anxiety disorders are divided into 2 groups: agora anxiety and special anxiety. The individual experiencing Social Anxiety is timid, introverted, shy, and has difficulty communicating when entering a new environment. In order to avoid criticism, people experience situations such as showing social attitudes, not being able to represent themselves and society. For this reason, the disorder can also be described as a disabling disorder. In general, for social anxiety disorder, avoidant attitudes arise from speaking in public, activities that highlight the self, and fearful concerns. Although it is expressed as a symptom, the situation is much more than these symptoms. (Kermen, Tosun and Doğan, 2016)

Social phobia is a type of anxiety that is based on individuals being judged by society, and which creates limited attitudes in their communication or avoidant or anxious attitudes about speaking in public and representing oneself and society. It is among the prominent findings in research that it is more common between the ages of 11-17. Social Anxiety Disorder (Social Phobia), which is one of the types of anxiety disorders, causes the individual to exhibit an avoidant attitude in the environment he/she is in , resulting in a decrease in the quality of life, and even considering that the adolescent population is at the stage of full professional career choices, it affects the future career choices of adolescents due to Social Anxiety Disorder. It can be said that it also affects

With the prediction that the perspectives of 17-year-old adolescents, who are the pre-voting age, on the political representation of women, will also affect the policy decisions, which are the primary triggers of important factors such as education, economy and understanding of life, which are the main variables of the country's future, in terms of the vision and mission of the society, the research was conducted in the senior year of high school. It is important to determine the degree of interest of students in politics in the context of variables such as gender, education, income level, parental attitude, residence, and to learn their perspectives on women's political representations, and to examine the relationship between women's political

representations in the context of gender and social anxiety disorder as a career choice. targeted. It is thought that studies in the field that include the research topic are insufficient . I have completed my thesis, which I wrote with the aim of contributing to the re-examination and restructuring of both the field and the place of women in terms of the place of women in Turkish society and their political representation in the context of gender, and the reflection of equal political administration on society.

, Prof., who contributed to my work in every process of this study . Dr. I would like to express my endless gratitude to Kürşat ŞAHİN YILDIRIMER.

both academically and (in today's world where all words and meanings containing " value " have become dull) throughout my work, with a note of "you are my dear " and "always stay with me";

"PRINCIPLED", whom I met during the Non-Thesis Master's Degree process, where I first stepped into the academic process, and who accepted my consultancy despite going through many tiring processes, and whose support I have always felt with me since then, who has led me in the formation of my professional choice in the Academy field, who is honest, student-centered, and whose absence is felt very much in the academic community. My esteemed teacher Prof., Head of the Department of Educational Management and Supervision, Akdeniz University Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Departments, who inspired me with his attitude. Dr. With a note of respect to "İlhan GÜNBAYI";

And especially;

My precious family, who is my constant supporter in every situation and situation, from the moment I start breathing on earth until the moment I end my breath ; My mother, Nürkiye OLD; With my endless love to my father, İbrahim ESKİ and my brother Ümit ESKİ ;

I would like to thank each and every one of them.

ENTRANCE

“The patriarchy of the new nation-state derives from the metaphor of femininity both for the purpose of modernization.
both in terms of ensuring national unity and the stability of the order
It is used as a symbolic element. Thus, women are now both
"They become the object of both state-centered (traditional) and state-centered
(modern) policies."
(Berkday, 2020: 560).

The most important indicator that distinguishes humans from other living creatures is that they are social beings. Individuals express their feelings and thoughts by communicating with other individuals or by performing with their behaviors. From past to present, people have to be in business, family and friend environments and communicate in these environments. Individuals who perform with their words or actions may sometimes encounter situations where their performance individually or in society causes anxiety, anxiety and panic. Due to the need arising from expressing oneself to people, the need to perform as an individual arises due to the necessity of being in career or social environments. At the point of these needs or requirements, the individual may sometimes have to communicate or perform without preparation, while sometimes being prepared. Individuals communicate with other people due to work-career, friendship, friendship communication or responsibilities. While this may sometimes involve speaking or performing among various audiences, it may also involve one-to-one communication or performing. Individuals with social anxiety, on the other hand, can be observed to turn to their own cognitive processes and remain in a state of intense anxiety, worry, panic or fear when they have to communicate or especially perform.

Social Anxiety Disorder is among the psychopathological disorders that are quite common today (estimated at 7%) and cause individuals to experience difficulties in their communication with each other, work, education and social life. Marx and Gelder (1960); It is seen that the intense anxiety and anxiety experienced by individuals when communicating or when they need to show themselves is defined as social anxiety. These symptoms also occur in different places and conditions. When individuals are eating, when they are in crowded entertainment and social environments such as parties, when communicating with someone for the first

time, when using toilets in public and private sectors, It is also observed that they experience social anxiety while using their devices . (Liebowitz 1987).

There are some criteria for the diagnosis of social anxiety, which is experienced in times and social environments when the individual needs to express himself. These are included in the 5th edition of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders. Disorders , Fifth Edition (DSM-5)].

diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental According to Disorders (DSM-5), it is observed that social phobia (anxiety) disorders are classified as "behavioral disorders showing symptoms of intense anxiety, worry, fear and panic". For social anxiety (social anxiety disorder); "It is a state of experiencing high-severity anxiety or panic that occurs when the individual is observed by either another individual or individuals or the society." we can say. (APA, 2013). It is known that it begins to be seen mostly in early adolescence or late childhood. (Pine and McClure , 2007). According to Kessler et al. (2005), although 5 years of age is the earliest age at which social phobia occurs, the age at which it reaches its highest rate for a 12-year-old individual is 12 years old. If treatment is not sought or precautions are not taken at these stages, it may progress to higher levels in adolescence and to a serious and chronic level in the phase of growth we call adulthood. (Yonkers , Dyck , & Keller, 2001).

Because people are social beings, they have to communicate, be in social environments, and perform, and although this situation creates a mild level of anxiety in most individuals, this rate can be high in some people. An anxiety level that has reached this level can be seen mostly in individuals at a level we call pathological. Although this situation is the same in adolescents, these symptoms are more common in introverted individuals. An adolescent who has experienced this situation will not be able to show himself in society in proportion to his anxiety level, and will often present an avoidant profile. As a result, it is normal for the adolescent to take a step back (French & Conrad, 2001) when it comes to tending to professions in front of the public, and in the social judgments that trigger this situation, the extra adolescent will exhibit actions and attitudes that will express/represent himself, both in his choice of profession. In addition, it can be said that adolescent individuals' exhibiting

shy/avoidant behavior causes them to fail in initiating social relationships, which is a necessity of social existence, and to experience situations such as difficulty in arguing and countertransference situations, depending on the conditions and situations (Jones, Hobbs , &Hockenbury , 1982). Since adolescence is actually a phase in which individuals become aware of their true selves and reveal themselves, it can be said that the social phobia they experience turns them into an avoidant, socially isolated personality, unable to express themselves appropriately, or avoidant when necessary. It can be seen that there are many studies in the literature on social anxiety. Especially when we look at the prevalence rate among adolescents , it is seen that it is in the range of 5%-15%. (Heimberg , Stein , Hiripi , & Kessler, 2000; Kessler et al ., 2005). In their research on adolescents, Bayramkaya , Toros and Özge (2005) observed that 14.4% of adolescents had social anxiety and that there was a positive correlation between social anxiety and depression. Looking at international analyses, the 1-year rate of social anxiety symptoms in the United States is 7%, but in many countries this rate is in the 0.5-2% range, according to DSM 5. When the Social Anxiety rate is evaluated in Europe, this rate appears to be 2.3%. When evaluated on an individual basis, it is seen that the same rate is found in adults and children and adolescents in Europe. (APA, 2013). It is among the observations that individuals with improved communication skills experience less social anxiety. For shy individuals, social communication, public speaking, and prepared or unprepared demonstration situations can be quite challenging.

Kapani (2003); While defining political participation, it is stated as "the tendency that shows the attitude of individuals within a society towards the political attitude and system of the country". In this sense, the individual shows his political attitude by wearing a badge, participating in the activities of the political party and voting, which is also mandatory for all citizens. When we look at the international political attitude and the political participation in our country, it is observed that there is more participation in our country. Although it is observed that the participation is high, unfortunately, compared to other countries regarding the political roles or political representation of women, the participation of women in our country (female political leader) stands out as 5% (2021 elections). (one). Again, there is a female minister in the Presidential cabinet (2). In the Turkish Grand

National Assembly, the rate of female deputies is 17.35%. (3) According to the UN research results, it is observed that our female representation rate is far behind at the international level. (Istanbul Political Research Institute, 2021). When all these data are considered together, it is important to reveal the reasons for the low representation of women in politics living in Turkey, which gained the right to vote and be elected before many developed countries (as early as December 5, 1934). It is thought that it is important to investigate the reasons for this minority situation in the political representation of women in our country, which gained the right to vote and be elected on December 5, 1934.

When we examine the gender element, which is one of the obstacles to women's political representation, if we start with the concept of gender, we can describe gender as biologically male and female. This element is expressed as a demographic element. The concept of gender is ; It expresses the meaning or expectation that the society and the culture in which it is located are placed on women and men. For example, in our country, women are seen as more suitable as teachers, while men are considered more suitable as crane operators , which is an important indicator in the context of gender roles . Atabey and Hasta (2018: 497), Gender has a serious impact on the individuals of the society. For example, "Which job would be suitable for an individual to work in?" How should gender affect family life? It is observed that gender roles have a significant impact on main factors such as "In which areas should an individual progress or stop depending on their gender?" When looked at in the context of the gender demographic variable, it is observed that women participate in politics at a very low rate, except for voting. (Ereş , 2006; Guldu and Ersoy-Kart, 2009). Women participate more by voting in our country. (Tatar, 2003: 348). When we look at the data of TÜSİAD (2001: 18), it is observed that women do not participate in participation such as wearing badges or engaging in active politics other than voting.

Housewifery and family duties, which were considered appropriate for women in the past, seem to pose an obstacle to women's political participation. (Kalaycıoğlu, 1983; Verba , Burns and Schlozman , 1997). More recently, an increase in the number of senior managers has been observed in direct proportion to the development of women's education levels. It is rarely seen that this situation also

spills over into political arenas . (Eser and Dinç, 2012; Fernandez- Ballesteros , Diez -Nicolas, Caprara , Barbaranelli and Bandura, 2002). In general, it is observed that in societies all over the world, women have to make more effort than men in both career and political fields. While men are characterized by more power and status, women are generally seen to be able to gain rights by working in a higher position in their career path. (Türkoğlu and Sayılan, 2016: 52). It is observed that the political participation rates in Turkey and the fact that men and women reach the desired point in climbing the political ladder are at the same level, but women face greater difficulties. (Kalaycıoğlu, 1983; Tatar, 2003; Eser and Sarışahin , 2016). Although the level of education and political participation make a positive contribution to a very small extent, it is still seen that in our country, women are busy with housework, while politics is defined as a man's profession. (Atabey and Hasta, 2018: 499) In a study conducted with 22nd term female MPs, it was found that the most important shield for women to take part in political circles is education. In conclusion, it can be concluded that education contributes greatly to socio- cultural change and women's political representation and participation . Studies stand out that the level of education affects the perspective of adolescents on the political roles and political representations of women in the context of gender, as well as many other factors such as the society they live in, their level of education, and economic conditions.

Gender role socialization, socio -economic variables, situational variables such as education level, marital status, profession and current political orientation cause the formation and perpetuation of gender discrimination in politics. Although there are many studies today that include politics , it is thought that there are many obstacles to the political representation of women both in the field and in the field. We can give a few reasons such as socio- cultural - socio -economic, personal characteristics of the individual and especially gender. It is thought that revealing the obstacles to women's political representation in our country is important for women who will work both in the field and in the field in the coming period. Again, in this study, the relationship between the attitudes of 17-year-old adolescents regarding the political representation of women and gender discrimination in Turkey and social phobia (social anxiety) was discussed. It is thought that it will reveal the possible

reasons for the gender differences in question , encourage women who want to take part in the political field in line with the findings, and make a positive contribution to the suggestions for women who want to have a say in this field, and will also contribute to researchers doing research in the field.

FIRST PART

1. CONCEPTUAL AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1.1. Social Anxiety Disorder

1.1.1. Definition and History

Phobia and Social wordsetymologyGreek and LatinIt goes up to . Phobia in GreekphobosradicallyWhile Socialis (produced for society) is derived fromThe word society (social) comes from Latinradicallyhas been formed .

Social AnxietyDisorder (SAD), Individual'ssocietyinbad , disturbeddisturbingOneto the situationfeeling of falling (judged)withyourselfheading towardslivefear , anxietystatusanxietydisorderTypeaspectis described.Individualliveanxietyreasonwithsocialto activitiescannot participate . In adolescentsIf this is the caseschoolfirstto beto , collectivelySAD occurs in areascomes out and the studentnecessaryacademicneed , professionalin his orientation , as well as his personality (self-respectdeprivation , being social , panic , etc.) . Social Phobia, in individuals , crying , self-latentarecreation , movementEffects such as deprivation etc.shapedcan be reflected . (DSM-5, 2013)

Beard uses the term "anthropophobia" The first one he used was in 1890.societyinfrom dialogueweldingfearaspectdefinitionSchilder also diagnosed SAD in 1938.involving ' socialterm ' neurosis 'withexplained.Clinicalsymptomaspectshameis and is in functionto the lossespathopenedstatingfindingsThere are . Full definition in DSM' Phobies ' by Janet in 903dessituationsas 'sociales 'has been defined . By definition , aggregatein areasspeech , collectivein the fieldpiano inability to play , writingto writefailaspectdiagnosedto eye(Albano et al., 1995). Marks and Gelder published Anxiety in 1966 .to groupshas separated . These groups,1. Social Anxiety , 2. Agoraphobia , AnimalPhobia in the form of Specific Phobiaand was first included in

the DSM possibility in recognition pioneer. One study occurrence and was first mentioned in DSM-III in 1980. In the environment others while there is food inability to eat, text inability to write, others next to you inability to work ways symptoms diagnosis of SF aspect place has received. In DSM-IV in addition to SF diagnosis observed degree anxiety symptom display from the situation anxiety hearing symptom, SF symptoms between including by making the disorder. It's called "Social Anxiety" Disorder as "has been diagnosed". (DSM-IV, 1994)

1.1.2. Social Anxiety according to DSM-5 disorder Diagnosis Criteria

Social Phobia (Social Anxiety) Diagnosis of the disorder according to DSM-5(2) criteria ;

1. ' A state of anxiety at a level that can be noticed in the society in which the individual lives. We can give examples such as speaking in public, asking for the right to speak in the community, eating, and initiating communication.
2. The person is afraid of behaving in a way that could be evaluated negatively or showing signs of anxiety (such as feeling humiliated or embarrassed, being ostracized by others, or causing offense to others).
3. These social situations almost always cause fear or anxiety.
4. The person avoids these social situations or endures them with intense fear or anxiety.
5. The fear or anxiety felt is disproportionate in the socio-cultural context, considering the situation feared in the social environments in question.
6. Fear, anxiety, or avoidance is persistent and lasts 6 months or longer.
7. The fear, anxiety, or avoidance causes clinically significant distress or impairment in social, occupational, or other important areas of functioning.
8. The fear, anxiety, or avoidance is not attributable to the physiological effects of a substance (a substance of abuse, a drug) or another health condition.

9. The fear, anxiety, or avoidance cannot be explained by another mental disorder, such as panic disorder, body dysmorphic disorder, or autism spectrum disorder.
10. If there is another health-related condition (Parkinson's disease, obesity, deformity from burns or injury), fear, anxiety, or avoidance are clearly unrelated to that condition.

If , at the moment of anxiety , the individual is speaking in front of the public or shows other signs of anxiety;

of SAD according to ICD 11 (22):

1. social interactions (e.g., having a conversation), being observed (e.g., eating or drinking), or performing in front of others (e.g., giving a speech).
2. The individual is concerned about behaving in a way that will be evaluated negatively by others or showing signs of anxiety.
3. Social situations are consistently avoided or endured with intense fear or anxiety.
4. Symptoms must persist for at least a few months.
5. Symptoms are severe enough to result in significant distress in personal, family, social, educational, occupational, or other important areas of functioning.'(DSM V)

1.1.3. Social Anxiety Causes and Symptoms of Disorder

When Social Anxiety disorders are examined, it is seen that physiological and psychological symptoms are generally observed. The individual thinks that he will be offended or humiliated by turning to himself if he is to speak in front of any public, and begins to experience physical symptoms that arise from mental delusions. Headache, facial redness, dry mouth, inability to speak, tremors, muscle tension , and palpitations are examples of these (Bögels , Alden , Beidel et al., 2010; Bendelow , Wedekind , 2014). Other personal factors that contribute to Social Anxiety (inability to communicate in society, lack of self-confidence, low self-esteem, hypersensitivity to criticism) can also be a factor in the formation or increase of an individual's social anxiety. (Noyan, Berk, 2007)

What we encounter in some of the physical symptoms of Social Anxiety Disorders is that while muscle tension is the primary symptom, these symptoms may cause distress in the person such as muscle stiffness, spasms, stiffness in the neck, and pain felt in the head (Aron, Harvey, Hainline, Hitchcock and Reardon, 2019, p. 779). Biologically, the individual experiencing Social Anxiety has a feeling of sudden heart palpitations, difficulty breathing, trembling in certain parts of the body (hands, feet), and normal levels of sweating, while psychologically, the individual has the feeling that he may suddenly encounter a bad situation. In the literature, as a differential diagnosis between panic attack disorder and anxiety, it is also seen that anxiety is defined as the state of experiencing fear against a feeling of limitation and directionless anxiety experienced by the individual in the face of a threatening situation from an unknown source. (Aron et al., 2019, p.781).

When SAD is examined in terms of children and adolescents, it is seen not only in situations where social performance can be performed, but also among their peers. Among the social anxiety symptoms of children, they may show behavioral anxiety symptoms such as shouting, avoiding talking in public, stamping, crying, remaining still, and hiding (DSM 5 R, 2013). Students experiencing Social Phobia may exhibit avoidant attitudes. Their participation in classes is low, their communication with their peers is at the maximum level, they are mostly a-social, recessive, do not have leadership qualities, and some of them may face focusing problems and learning difficulties (Bernstein, Bernat, Davis et al., 2007). When it reaches even more advanced levels, the student may create his own latent space and think that social isolation is healthier for him, and in his post-school life he may become less social, unable to display his own talents, introverted, unable to express and represent himself and the society, lacking the ability to represent himself in his career choices. If there is, they may face situations such as turning to different professions due to social phobia, not being able to show their true skills, exclusion and high anxiety when they have to perform in business life or social areas. (Bandelow, Wedekind, 2014)

of social anxiety disorder cannot be clearly distinguished, multiple predispositions are evident. It can be seen that genetic factors, traumatic (emotional) experiences in the early stages, observation of parental attitudes, determining anyone

as a model, biological confusion of the brain, and biological and psychological reasons may be involved. Mostly, in the past history of the symptom, it is observed that people were repressed in childhood, but they are also shy and timid, and if there are findings that occur in childhood and adolescence, it can be seen that they may be absent from school and as a result, they become individuals who withdraw from school and have social anxiety. (Evren, 2010, p.495

Individuals with Social Anxiety become shy and avoidant in speaking, eating, and standing out in society. Accordingly, they prefer to stay away from activities that will highlight their active self, such as speaking in public, taking the floor, making presentations, or they may exhibit shy attitudes when interacting. If this situation progresses, it can cause situations such as isolation of the person from society or not being able to defend their rights, and it can also cause the person to become introverted in temperament and have low self-esteem.

It is important to distinguish Social Anxiety Disorder from stranger anxiety and social withdrawal disorders in the early childhood stage. While periodic anxiety of children and adolescents in early childhood can be considered normal as it contributes positively to their physical and psychological development, distinguishing between anxiety, which can turn a child or adolescent into a pathological course outside its normal course, is necessary and important for the healthy life cycle of the individual. Developmental normal anxiety disorder symptoms of children and adolescents can mostly be evaluated in terms of environment and stress factors and may not be distinguished from anxiety requiring treatment. (Manassis , Tannock and Young 2007, p.5)

1.1.4. Social Anxiety Treatment of Disorder Methods

be applied as separate processes . The main factor that determines this distinction is the phenomenon of the individual diagnosed with social phobia. The most preferred method is the Cognitive Behavioral Therapy method known as CBT (Lopes , Albano, 2013). CBT is a treatment method that includes a 4-stage process (first stage: psychoeducation, 2nd stage: cognitive restructuring, 3rd stage: social skills training, 4th stage: exposure) (Bandelow , Wedekind , 2014). Let's say the case is a female candidate who wants to enter politics. Diagnosis: social anxiety. In

the first stage, the client is given general information about social anxiety disorder and treatment processes. In the second stage, an imaginary and fictional cognitive process of how the individual can communicate in an environment or with a friend, how to speak in any society is covered, and at this stage, a bad situation (making a bad speech, blushing, not being able to speak, etc.) is also discussed. It is assumed that even in the worst cases, knowing the process can provide comfort to the client. In the third stage, the person is able to first initiate and continue the conversation and finally end it, express an opinion in any conversation process, share about himself, listen with attention, make or reject a request from the other person, express and receive appreciation, criticize and react in case of criticism. Practice processes are carried out to increase social skills through activities such as giving a speech, etc. In the last stage, the individual needs to give a speech, for example, in any environment in order to experience the treatment processes he has acquired in such an environment (Spence , Donovan , Brechman , 2000).

Another treatment method for children and adolescents, in addition to CBT, is the social effectiveness method defined as SET (Beidel , Turner, Morris, 2000; Beidel , Turner, Sallee , 2007). In this method, a process is followed in the form of psychoeducation involving the family, social skills training (rehearsal techniques, peer exercises, homework, modeling) and exposure, which includes a monitored process. The process takes approximately 12 weeks, one week of which takes place with a group. In a study where SET was applied to the 8-12 age group, a significant improvement was observed compared to the control group. Again, while an improvement in the diagnosis of SAD was observed in 67% of the clients, the rate in the control group was 5%. (Beidel , Turner, Morris, 2000) In SAD in adolescents, techniques containing two types of scales can be applied along with the Adolescent Cognitive Behavioral Group Therapy (E-GBBT) as methods to improve the skills related to ASSB (Academic and Social Success) in school and classroom environments . These are the Adolescent Cognitive Behavioral Group Therapy methods defined as SET (social effectiveness method)-Ç and E-GBBT . (Masia , Fisher, Shrout , Rathor , 2007)

1.1.5. Social Anxiety of disorder Importance of Treatment

Social Phobia is a state of fear that a person feels because of the anxiety that he will be humiliated in society. This affects the individual's life satisfaction due to various variables (career, economic, family - social environment, communication, self and society representation, self-worth, self-esteem). When the researches are examined, it is observed that their number is insufficient. Although various methods are shown in the treatment of Social Anxiety, it is thought that the treatment of social anxiety disorder is important for healthy generations, a life with functional life satisfaction, and as a result, a healthy, productive and peaceful and happy society, which has decreased considerably today.

1.1.6. Quality of Life in Social Anxiety Disorder

Researchers' tendencies towards this concept are seen as it provides the basis for the individual to experience a healthier psychology and physical processes while maintaining his/her daily life, which expresses the quality of life. It is seen that it has a negative impact on the quality of life of the individual diagnosed with social anxiety disorders because it affects the individual's attitude towards life (Wittchen , Biloch , 1996). The individual may experience difficulties in communication such as work, social environment, and family communications. Frequently feeling nervous while in society, exhibiting an avoidant attitude in situations where performance requires a display of self, and a decrease in the level of academic achievement compared to the past, which is frequently encountered for children and adolescents, can be observed (Van Ameringen , Mancini , Farvolden , 2003). In fact, students may experience serious absenteeism and fail the class as a result (Davidson, Hughes, George, Blazer , 1993; Last , Strauss, 1990). The striking finding in a study conducted by Wittchen and Beloch (1996) is that 8% experienced job loss due to the diagnosis of social anxiety disorder, and 23.3% experienced interference in their work-related performance. In the family dimension, it is seen that the preference for living alone is higher (Schneier , Johnson, Horning , Liebowitz , Weissman , 1992;Norton, McLeod , Guertin 1996). Another finding seen in individuals with Social Phobia is that suicidal thoughts and attempts increase. (Davidson, Hughes, George, Blazer , 1993, Schneier , Johnson, Horning , Liebowitz , Weissman , 1992).

In a study conducted in a group of people with social phobia, it can be said that one-third of the participants had suicidal thoughts, which is a remarkable rate (Lepine , Lellouchh , 1995). Reactions such as lack of ability to represent the society and oneself and introversion can also be observed in their professional choices due to the prejudices of the society. Data show that quality of life and occupational satisfaction are closely related to social anxiety disorder, highlighting the importance of diagnosis and treatment.

1.1.7. Social Anxiety Analysis of Disorder in the World and Turkey

Social Phobia, Person's society in negative , shame transmitter with a situation opposite across can stay concern with society in pathological One anxiety legislative is the situation . (Evren, 2010, p.474)

It is seen that the Social Phobia Working Group formed by the World Psychiatric Association collects the symptoms of social anxiety in 3 items. (Montgomery, 1995, cited in: Yolaç , 1996:55):

These;

1. Anxiety that one's actions and words will be observed and evaluated and judged by someone else in the community.
2. Anxiety about making a performance/presentation for fear that it will be embarrassing or humiliating, either individually or in public.
3. It can be said that it is listed as 'showing avoidant personality indicators in situations that create or will create panic/fear or anxiety'.

literature Considering the rate of 12.1% with four ranked (first major depression comes second _next alcohol addiction third next specific from anxiety) received Results is between . Social Anxiety in the USA Disorder: 2 - 13 % in values is seen . In the West, these rates seem to vary between 0.5% and 16%. In Eastern societies, Social Anxiety Disorder is less seen . here your criteria mostly inside found society cultural norm values with related is (Evren, 2010, p.477)

Turkey Social Anxiety disorder with relating to carried out are ain their work widespread One psychological discomfort aspect what's that came out can be said .

Social anxiety (social phobia / anxiety) studies in Turkey are mostly screening and correlation studies (Aydın and Tekinsav -Sütçü, 2007; Eriş and İkiz, 2013; Erkan, 2002; Gültekin and Dereboy , 2011; Hamarta , 2009; Keskin and Orgun , 2007; Palancı, 2004; Solmaz, Gökalp, and Babaoğlu, 1999), and studies aimed at treating anxiety are few in number. (Aydın, Tekinsav -Sütçü and Sorias , 2010; Eren Gümüş, 2002; Koçak, 2001; Nedim Bal and Öner, 2014). Social anxiety is a type of psycho - disorder that is suitable for treatment in the educational environment of the individual at the point of psychosocial intervention . (Fisher, Masia -Warner and Klein , 2004; Ryan and Warner, 2012) a. It is thought that early psychosocial treatment for adolescents with high levels of social anxiety is effective in reducing social anxiety levels, but in case of intervention before adolescence , it can prevent the emergence of anxiety symptoms. In general, in the literature, there are treatment studies aimed at reducing intense anxiety rather than completely treating social phobia. (Goldin et al ., 2012; Moscovitch et al ., 2012; Segool and Carlson 2008). When we look at the studies on treatment for children and adolescents, it is mostly cognitive. -Although behavioral group therapy studies are available, school-based preventive treatment methods are also encountered. (Fedoroff and Taylor, 2001; Heimberg , 2001; Öst , Cederlund and Reuterskiöld , 2015; Rowa and Antony, 2005; Fisher, Maisa -Warner and Klein , 2004)

1.2.Gender

1.2.1.Sex, Gender

1.2.1.1. Gender

gender is defined in the Turkish Language Association as a differential feature transferred to a person during creation, which gives people reproductive differences. (TDK, 2020). This distinction, which is transferred to the individual from birth, is a demographic characteristic that cannot be changed over time. (Sage , 2014). A characteristic transferred to a person without his/her will can also be defined as a biological phenomenon. We can say that it is a privilege gained outside the individual. (Özcan, 2012:5).

While gender refers to a status that an individual acquires outside of himself, this natural status that a person acquires is defined with roles by the society

he lives in. In a way, it reveals the cultural-social-economic expectations and roles that society imposes on the individual. (Bhasin , 2003; Dökmen, 2012; Oakley , 1985). The perception of the feminine and masculine segments in the society they live in, their thinking , eating, drinking, sitting, and their roles in almost all processes of life are shaped from the very beginning, and expectations are formed by the society, and positive or negative judgment situations in line with the roles and attitudes are also formed. It is in some kind of formation in terms of value judgments. This situation may also be very diverse in that it varies from society to society. It can be said that gender is a multidimensional concept. (Akın and Demirel, 2003; Altınova and Duyan, 2013; Kottak , 2002; Staggenborg , 1998). Although there have been some changes in the roles of men and women over time, society in general has assigned certain economic and social roles to individuals as men and women in life. (Aksoy, 2006). When evaluated in this respect, gender also has a dynamic nature. We can say that the biggest indicator of this is that it can take shape from society to society and according to the cultural values and norms. (Bhasin , 2000; Oakley , 1985)

1.2.1.2. Gender

are subject to discrimination between men and women based on their democratic qualities in the society they live in. It is the social structure that shapes the individual's lifestyle, beliefs , clothing style, and even eating and drinking qualities. This role appears as the first step in the family, which is the smallest structural unit of society. We can describe the family as the first mechanism for raising the individual in accordance with these roles . It shapes people's qualities such as how men and women will behave in line with their creations, how they will move, how they will eat and drink, and what professions they will take part in, in line with the values and beliefs of the society in which they are raised. At this point , the main factor is society and the individual continues his life with the gender factor in line with the variable of society. Since gender includes many variables, it can be said that it is generally multidimensional and permeates people's lives in line with many concepts such as society's perception of life, culture, economy, and political conjuncture , and this is not a written rule but is implicitly reflected on people. Although this produces good results in many aspects, it is also seen that it creates

grounds for inequality between women in developing countries in terms of gender beliefs and value judgments. Considering that the gender variable defines women's workload as home duties in daily life, and men's job duties as hunters and carriers, it can be said that this causes an inequality in the task definitions of men and women. In conclusion, it can be said that the concept of gender is a phenomenon that should be given importance for social welfare. (Vatandaş, 2007) The concept of gender appears as a reflection of the roles assigned to individuals as a type of creation. Another variable we encounter here is the concept of Culture, and culture is a phenomenon that attributes the thoughts, perceptions, actions and attitudes of individuals to the individual . (Taşkın and Terzioğlu, 2008). Although the two concepts are seen as intertwined with each other, it is seen that a distinction was first made in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Here , it is seen that gender is defined as a purely anatomical feature and is a phenomenon called innate, while gender is defined as a phenomenon that is acquired later and shaped according to the cultural, social and society in which we live. The concept of gender is a multidimensional phenomenon, and one of these dimensions is gender roles; It can also be defined as the set of attitudes, actions and behaviors attributed by the society according to gender, depending on the society in which it is grown. Male and female individuals are expected to gain a life perspective in line with the expectations of society (Dökmen, 2012). In a traditionalist society, gender roles define housework roles for women, while men portray the role of breadwinner. In contemporary societies; Women and men are defined as equal roles, which means that both men and women are assigned to do housework and earn a living (Akın and Demirel, 2003; Basow , 1992; Dökmen, 2012). While gender is a status that the individual acquires outside himself, the society in which he lives is all about the individual. can affect your life. Society is the first factor here and affects the individual's entire life, such as how he will eat, where and how he will live, where he will laugh and where he will cry. In this respect , it can be said that it is very important in terms of defining the gender roles of the society we live in (Kalav , 2012: 150).

1.2.2. Gender Roles and Development

1.2.2.1. Role

The role is acquired later and directly by the society in which the individual breathes . The role of the facts that the discipline of sociology gives priority to is the attitudes and actions expected from the individual according to the society in which they live.

1.2.2.2. Gender Roles

It is a behavioral motif that is expected from an individual based on his/her innate male and female status and the society in which he/she belongs, that is undertaken against his/her will, and that is attributed by the society (Günay and Bener, 2011).

Özcan (2012; 12- 14) The individual learns these attributed role expectations first from his family, and then through factors such as his social environment, relatives, school, teacher, books, and mostly through subliminal ways. He learns the values, beliefs and expectations of the society, family, social and business environment in which he lives, sometimes consciously and sometimes unconsciously, from infancy. Dressing girls in pink when they are born, choosing dolls as toys for girls, choosing blue for boys, choosing toys such as guns and cars can be given as examples of these subliminal beliefs, expectations and value judgments. In a sense, gender roles can be expressed as the totality of attitudes and behaviors expected by society based on the anatomical structures of individuals as men and women (Bingöl, 2014).

the characteristics of a quality that starts from a young age and continues when the child grows up, and is transferred through a kind of reinforcement (Zeyneloğlu, 2008). The concept of gender stereotypes is another important concept that stands out here. Masculine and feminine qualities as gender appear as a kind of cognitive schemas shared by society. Gender stereotypes include various components . Examples of these include biological visibility, temperament, beliefs, actions and attitudes that form identity (Deaux and Lewis, 1984). According to gender stereotypes, for example, women are described as more emotional and feminine as

personal characteristics, while men are judged as more materialistic, rational and masculine. In this judgment, women are expected to have a more emotional temperament and choose their professional orientation in line with this tendency, while men are expected to choose their professional tendencies due to their masculine nature (Aydın and Kavuncu, 1991). If we express these with more concrete qualities, the qualities expected from the masculine are rationalist, active, rational, cold-blooded, assertive, safe, fearless, independent, strong, tough, aggressive; It is seen that the qualities expected from the feminine are called equivalent qualities with adjectives such as low self-esteem, loving, sensitive, naive, emotional, harmonious, accepting, moderate, modest, well-groomed, constantly caring, dependent, passive, compassionate, accepting (DeLisi and Soundranayagam, 1990; Dökmen, 2012; Eagly, Wood and Diekman, 2010; Sunar, 1982). As can be seen, gender roles assign a passive role to women, while a confident and active role is assigned to men (Burger, 2006). It can be said that underdeveloped countries where patriarchal structural patterns dominate are also an important factor in shaping gender roles. It can be said that in these societies, women are more of a secondary gender, the aggregator of men. It can be said that the priority given to men emerges as a hegemonic structure and continues as a cultural phenomenon. (Cangöz, 2013). Inferring from this, gender stereotypes reveal the distinction between masculine and feminine gender due to their anatomy from the very beginning, and it can be stated that the inequality created is also a factor in the social cultural inheritance (Altınova and Duyan, 2013). Gender stereotypes play an important role in the lives of both masculine and feminine. It can create problems in individuals' ability to reveal their true self in line with their own self-awareness (Evans and Diekman, 2009). This distinction, which gives rise to social inequality, can also be the basis for being transmitted from generation to generation by society. While women are in the background, men are always the decision-making center and are described as an emotionless being, so this ongoing structure is transferred from communities to societies as a result of value judgments. These stereotypes, which are tangential to the concepts of both equality of opportunity and freedom, bring about freedom of choice, education and career choice, and the situation of not being partners in decisions (Zeyneloğlu 2008). In our country, which is one of the developing countries where traditional values are carefully preserved, gender stereotypes are a

result of the patriarchal structure. Judgments are present in all areas of life of individuals and are one of the areas where social inequality is experienced (Kahraman, Ozansoy, Smart, Kekillioğlu , & Özcan, 2014). It can be stated that despite the difficult conditions brought by economic processes, gender judgment patterns still create serious inequality in working life . Due to this situation, it is seen that women are still unable to work comfortably in the fields they want in their working lives or they face gender judgment stereotypes when they want to move up. The fact that there are few women in the political field in our country, where some professions are classified as women's and some professions are classified as men's, can be shown as an example of this situation. Considering that development has spread to every field, it can be said that this inequality has decreased slightly as the change in education and income levels is positive (Attanapola , 2004).

1.2.3. Gender-Based Discrimination and Division of Labor

If we examine the gender roles of men and women from past to present, it is evident in the literature that they are generally examined in the context of division of labor and the stages of differences in these processes stand out. The concept of family came to the fore after the transition from hunting and gathering to settled life, which was noticeable during the stages of hunting, gathering, the development of animal husbandry and the development of weaving. With this process, the first steps of the inequality process, which we call separation, have been taken , with women doing more of the housework and the division of labor such as gathering and hunting brought by men , and the division of duties such as cooking the food brought by men at home and housework . As the development process continued, women were busy with tasks such as raising children, housework, and men were busy with tasks such as harvesting land and agricultural products . One of the biggest factors in the role sharing here is the internalization of roles such as housework and child care for women. By the 1930s , the concept of gender discrimination gradually emerged. It is seen that measurement tools aimed at detecting this noticeable distinction in research are gradually appearing in the literature. The aim of the measurement tools is to minimize or even eliminate gender deviations. Another important development that stands out this year is that the concept of "social role" can be used within gender. As time passed (1940), the

concept of gender took a more concrete expression and the concept of "female and male roles" emerged (Connell, 2017). It is seen that the concepts of masculine and feminine roles are used together with gender roles and age over time. If these roles are evaluated in terms of gender roles, biological factors, which are the anatomical structure of the individual, are very important factors for the individual. Because it can be said that the individual is important because he has roles that society expects from him before he is born, due to his innate gender. It can be stated that the gender characteristic of the individual is important for his/her place in the living space due to the fact that the roles expected from the masculine role and the feminine role differ. (Bingöl, 2014). It can be said that gender role stereotypes have a restrictive nature in many ways if the individual is in a traditional society, as he/she will have a lifestyle according to the stereotypes of the traditional society he/she is in, whereas if he/she is in a contemporary society, he/she will be able to exhibit more self-aware behaviors and attitudes, which means he/she will be more aware of his/her self. It can be stated that it can reveal the indicators of being a happy and healthy individual. Because the entire life of the individual is shaped by the society he lives in. In this case, it brings out an inference that it develops on the basis of the gender factor. While the masculine individual is expected to be determined, rational, breadwinner, arrogant, and whose emotions are ignored, the feminine is more naive, passive, carries out the housework, raises children, cares, etc. A structure that shows signs of lack of self-worth, such as an accepting, patient and silent structure, stands out. Expectations are generally based on this in society (Keskin and Ulasan, 2018). What is noticeable in the division of housework is that, while the male individual's expectations are for jobs that involve the power factor, such as gardening and repairs, women's job description expectations such as ironing, cleaning, cooking, and child care stand out. Today, although there is no field where development is not experienced, changes in perception, albeit small, are noticeable in the job descriptions of people in society. Although there has been a considerable change in women's struggle to survive in business life, including in our country, compared to the past, there is a change, albeit not at a sufficient level, and a slight change in the distribution of household duties can be mentioned (Günay and Bener, 2011). According to a study (Dökmen, 2016), constant behaviors and attitudes reveal the concept of normalization in society. Since women constantly do housework, cooking,

child care, etc., society now considers this as a woman's job and duty and turns it into a belief and value judgment . As a result of this, gender role stereotypes emerge (Dökmen, 2016).

The individual learns to act in line with the teachings of the society he is in. Due to the fact that he does not see different perspectives in line with the teachings in society, he considers it as a normal and natural attitude and behavior and exhibits the behavior and attitude that society expects from him. Since that individual will continue the same pattern to their children, the gender stereotype continues. (Erdoğan, 2016). These rigid and universal gender stereotypes become an established stereotype of that society after a while and become established as a kind of belief. (Seçgin , 2012). The individual first receives gender stereotypes from the family, which is the smallest structural unit of society, which we call the growing area and which cares for him/her before the social area recognition phase. Subsequently, as a result of being a social being, the process continues with relatives, social environment, school and work. Individuals in the school phase between the ages of 6 and 18, which we call the growth phase, are most open to development among adolescents. It is the stage when it is most open to learning , therefore , its importance in transferring stereotypes about gender roles to children and adolescents with sometimes explicit and sometimes covert messages is quite noticeable. At these age stages, the degree of ownership of stereotypes may increase as a result of social communication and learning at school. The study conducted by Condry and Condry (1976) involving university students attracts attention in this regard. In this study, a 9-month-old baby plays with a toy for children studying at school. It was stated that some of the students participating in the study said that the baby playing the game was a girl, and the other part said that it was a boy. In line with this statement, it was observed that they stereotyped the child's play style. (Condry and Condry , 1976). This situation shows that patriarchal perceptions attributed to gender arise from social stereotypes. In this case, it also reveals gender discrimination. In conclusion, despite the existence of equal rights, gender roles have a negative impact on women due to the gender factor, and they cannot benefit from the legal rights stated as equal to the extent they should. (Orloff , 1993). Because individuals are equipped with social stereotypes, even if unintentionally, from the moment they are born. This

perception, which flourishes in the family, continues with friends, relatives and social circle, as well as in business life. While the girl child grows up extremely meticulous in need of protection, at the same time , the child subliminally learns qualities such as being normative, learning to accept, weak in terms of self-worth, and passive, even in the first growth phase. The best example of this is that the caregiver qualification begins when a baby is given to them when they are still a child. Concepts of personal self-worth in business life are almost non-existent, and although it is not compulsory for her to work, the girl learns and is taught, consciously or unconsciously, qualities such as being a good wife and mother, and being obedient, when she is a child. The boy, on the other hand, is fearless, breaks, breaks, wanders, dusts, learns his freedom and determination, and hunting status when he is a child. The gun toy given to him is an example of this inevitable situation. He learns, especially when he is a child, that he will be weak if he shows his emotions, and that he will be weak if he shows his emotions. (Perception: “A man does not cry!”, “A man does not show his emotions !” etc.) They always have to be strong. They are always expected to be courageous. He can go whenever he wants and communicate with whomever he wants. Responsibility is instilled from childhood through a good job and providing for one's family. This responsibility actually gives challenging responsibilities to both genders, and disruption of social peace may occur with the arrival of unhappy individuals. It can also be said that today's economic conditions require both individuals to work, which can create problems in overly traditionalist families in terms of roles. Ready-made schemas presented to individuals may seem challenging if the conditions are opposite. Conflicts in marriage, beliefs, clothing, home and individual expected roles, which are considered normal cultural norms in society, can be considered as examples of these ready-made schemes. Another example of stereotypical social judgment is the belief that it would be wrong for a woman to speak in front of a man out of respect. (Berkday, 2016). This stereotype of gender judgment, which includes the submission of women and shows the dominance of men (İmançer , 2006). Since men and women who grow up with this disorder will continue to hold the same judgment when they grow up, women cannot make any skills or choices in business life or the political field due to their lack of self-worth. While this situation gives negative space to the female individual, it can be said that it also creates inequality in terms of

rights. Since men grow up with the perception that they can do anything and that women are always in the background, they will always hold them back in terms of their right to speak, and women will be deprived of their legal rights. It can be said that these gender stereotypes, which pose an obstacle to social equality and prevent women, are not only a socio-economic reflection, but also a prediction that they will have a negative impact and create a negative obstacle in the development of the country compared to countries competing with digital technologies, both socially, culturally and economically. can be done. Our country is still among the developing countries due to its social structure that has digested this structure well. Gender discrimination, which is considered one of the biggest factors, has a significant impact on all administrative areas of the country (social, economic, political, working life, etc.). Despite many steps towards democratization, women's inequality is observed in every area of society (Özyaydinlik , 2014: 94-95). In a study, a different theory on the subject was put forward. In the study (Bora 2012: 5), as a reason for gender, in the division of labor, people tend to work areas that are the result of their physical (strong-weak) structures due to their gender- biological differences. He states that it emerged as a belief that describes the feminine side as having a structure that waits for the house and does the housework due to its weak body, while the masculine side, being fearless and strong, brings food to the house and provides the livelihood of the house. As a result, in the house of women, women are passive, lacking in self-worth, and are in the background, while men are strongly dominant, actively structured (Habermas , 2010: 103) social network, which has become normalized over time and cultural task distribution has been imposed on individuals as it has been for years. While the woman, as a matter of fact, is a mother and is deployed to her home, her children and her husband, the woman is left out of business life as a result of the man being the breadwinner of the house. With the ossification of the concept of equality of opportunity, women have always tried to take part in concepts such as education and having a profession by coming from behind, even if they are either completely excluded or in competition with men by fighting against inequalities. Being considered less preferred than men in business life (given birth, maternity leave, child care leave, breastfeeding leave, being considered an emotional being, she cannot make good decisions, etc.), lack of equal salary even if she starts working, lack of social security, glass ceiling syndrome. Due

to factors such as childhood , they are not treated equally in business life (Çakır, 2008: 43-45). While it is deemed appropriate for women to take care of the house as a result of gender roles, if they work, the division of labor at home is imposed on women, so disruptions in housework are evaluated only because of women and women are blamed. In this case, it puts the woman in a very difficult position. Considering that the society consists of male and female individuals, the social structure will bring about problems as unhappy women will give birth to unhappy children and unhappy families. For men, the inability to support the household , which occurs due to the difficult conditions of a single working parent in today's conditions due to the role of being responsible for supporting the household, makes the man feel powerless and weak, and invites a psychologically unhealthy environment (tense, angry and conflicts), and violent tendencies, women. It seems that it brings with it many problems such as murders and divorces. It can be said that the validity of gender perceptions today brings with it a problem for both men and women. In this case, it can be said that it creates an uneasy society and a troubled country. The concept of gender perception is formed by norms shaped according to the society in which we live. (Özkazanç , 2010: 45). While this separation from the nature of belief was perhaps considered normal in the past, the digital age has now distanced individuals from this belief structure .

The most important indicator that draws attention in the concept of gender is that it draws attention to the discrimination between men and women and is against this discrimination. This concept stands out because it is against all social, biological and social discrimination between men and women. His main point is that he criticizes this situation. (Dedeoğlu, 2000: 139-142). It can be said that this concept is a reaction to the prejudices that society attributes to individuals. (Alptekin, 2011: 35)

1.2.4. Gender Equality

There is equality between men and women, but there are differences between regions, countries, and even local gender , resulting in a situation of inequality in which women are mostly negatively affected. While the concept of gender equality refers to the fact that women and men have the same rights in all areas such as social, business, economic, legal and political fields, regardless of

gender, gender inequality is the opposite of this situation, which is socio- economic , political, labor rights in all areas of society. It is a phenomenon where men and women are separated in all areas such as the home. Here, men and women do not experience equal opportunities. There is an inequality of opportunity (Ecevit, 2003). Currently, women experience inequality in different positions and levels, and it can be stated that these are mostly de facto inequality (Bakırcı, 2012). Stating that people are equal from birth, Sancar (2000)' s statement that what he means by equality is 'male, property owner and white' people shows that no matter where they are, men and women are equal in almost every field (social, economic , political, etc.). They are faced with inequality (Sancar, 2000: 199-200). Considering that the development of a society is possible with the efforts of all individuals who make up the society, it is obvious that gender stereotypes created based on individual biological factors such as men and women will not have a positive effect on the progress of a society. We can talk about success if both men and women participate in every field, and both men and women should be able to speak up in political, social and working life and reflect their positive effects that include their whole self, so that the society can achieve the level of welfare. In this respect, the meaning and importance of the country's management is quite high. The importance of this aspect in the necessary political decisions to eliminate existing disparities, including biological elements, cannot be ignored. For this reason , it is important not to ignore the effects that will eliminate all the discriminatory factors that may arise between men and women in all areas such as social, political and business . It is important to strategically target the needs of women and activities that will eliminate inequality and make women's lives easier (Sancar et al., 2006: 180). It is among the targets as a strategic plan that is addressed every year in political processes or by commercial and social institutions in business life and by institutions and individuals in individual fields . It can be stated that all the constructive work of women in the political, economic and social fields will contribute greatly to the development of society . All national institutions, councils and states, including our country, such as the Council of Europe and the United Nations, refer to the existing issue of gender equality as a serious problematic phenomenon, and it is seen that various commissions, negotiations, legal processes and regulations are carried out. (Sayer , 2011: 46-61)

1.3. Politics, Political Participation

of the study This first in the section politics concept will be explained . subsequently political participation phenomenon and political participation determining factors main theme of the study the one which... psychological factors , gender Working as a factor the themes subheadings containing _ _ _ place will be given . Moreover Political of representation Gender Between also includes distribution will give .

1.3.1. Politics

Politics , in a society management and managed between management power the one which... of power using , managing and managed between your interests together adaptation aspect can be defined . power this management power with provides . (Dursun, 2002). Here aim all society in individuals promise right taking One Another expression with opportunity equality with 18 years old above individuals political tools (voting , election applicant being poster _ using pressing etc.) vote process offer again _ This vote process post-audit making and healthy One way This stop the process aspect expression can be done . In this field discipline the one which... Political Sciences if , the mentioned from the very beginning of the election (to the election applicant becoming) from of the process to end much last processes objectives , necessary situations and conditions , affecting factor on many areas such as determining knowledge learning and presenting aim acquirer One is discipline .

1.3.2. The Phenomenon of Political Participation

It is possible to talk about the existence of democracy in the country with political participation. It also means that the individual participates in political activities and processes and is informed about the functions and processes. The individual participating in the activities of the ruling party and political parties is an important phenomenon for both self-worth gain and healthy social processes, especially when he takes part in decision-making processes. Moreover, with participation, the individual can become more willing and create a field of work as well as a profession . The concept of social state is one of the general principles of

the state , and this is possible with democracy, that is, with individuals taking part in every political step and field, regardless of gender. (Kaypak, 2011: 33) Another researcher seems to define political participation as the act of being active in political decisions through the participation of individuals in decision-making in political processes. (Kalaycıoğlu, 1984: 199).

Deniz Baykal has tried to classify participation in political processes. In this order, it is classified as following political events and phenomena in the first place, in the second place as developing an attitude towards the political events that have occurred or are expected to occur, and in the third and last place as being involved in political events. Following political events and facts is the first thing in the phenomenon of political participation; While the individual is informed about political events through newspapers, internet, magazines or processes such as conferences, rallies and congresses, when the second classification is made, the individual moves to the stage of sharing and transferring the impressions and information he has obtained in line with his impressions with his close circle, spouse and friends. In the third process, which is the last one , the individual is now directly involved in political processes and actively participates. In this process, the individual can join political parties. He can become a candidate and take actions and attitudes such as marching. (Dahl , 2010: 56; Baykal, 1970: 31-34)

Milbrath (1977) divided political participation into three stages. In the first phase of these stages, it refers to the citizen's having an opinion about political events, attitudes and facts, which he describes as audience activities. Citizens provide this in ways such as the press, communication tools, and rallies. In the second phase, transition activities, the citizen takes an attitude with the knowledge of political events and provides access, albeit to a small extent. In the final phase, which is gladiatorial activities, the individual now actively gains access to political events. This may include activities such as becoming a candidate, organizing a rally, being an active member, and running election campaigns (Quoted by: Afacan, 1994: 14).

When political participation is examined by gender, it is observed that there are very few female political representatives in countries with traditional values. The field of politics, which is perceived as male representation, does not

identify with the concept of democracy. Democracy means equality as a concept and includes women and men having equal rights in all areas. It is thought that the main reason behind the low participation of women in the political field is the perception of gender. Due to gender perception, women either cannot continue or cannot exist in politics. In line with biological factors, before birth, there is a scale of expectations, almost taboo, about what kind of clothes and food men and women will wear, where they will go and what profession they will perform, and the individual adapts to this presented style. Since women's living space is limited to the home, they have difficulty even entering business life and can rarely take part in the political arena. This situation puts women in a disadvantaged position. In a globalizing world, many needs for life are taking shape, and countries' needs are met mostly by the masses who hold the political management power. This political group, if there is only a male section, may lead to women's needs not being met adequately. While the aim of the political process is to ensure that social interests are taken into consideration, we cannot say that only a male-dominated political administrator can provide a full and sufficient level of welfare among the public. For this reason, it is thought that women's participation in political processes and management is important in reaching the entire grassroots mass. In this thesis, it is thought that it is important to reveal the reason for this lack of representation of female politicians, who are very few in the political field. Considering that senior high school students, who target an important audience in the election process and will vote for the first time, will vote after finishing school, it is thought that it is important to learn the political tendencies of the young audience, their political participation, and their perspectives on women's political participation. Considering the influence of adolescents, who include a significant number of people who will vote, in the formation of society and in the selection of individuals who will participate in political management, which will have a significant impact on all areas of life, social, economic, technological and cultural, the effect of adolescents' voting in shaping the society cannot be ignored. For this reason, the study is thought to be important.

1.3.3. Factors Determining Political Participation

When people participate in political processes or political activities in their society, they participate based on various factors. Variables such as age, gender,

profession, social initiative level, psychological effects, and civic awareness are important factors for the individual in political participation. Factors such as the country you are in, the country's political conjuncture , election perception, and political parties are also among the important factors in political participation. In this thesis, only socio- economic factors, psychological factors and especially the gender factor, which is the main theme of the thesis, will be discussed among the factors that determine political participation in line with the aims of the thesis.

1.3.3.1. Socio -economic Factors

socio- economic factors are examined, a multi-dimensional structure emerges. These factors include the individual characteristics of the individual who will participate politically. Factors such as the individual's education level, profession, economic level, individual's income level, age, city of residence, religious belief, psychological perception, and gender are examples of these.

1.3.3.1.1. Psychological Factors

Human is a social entity. For this reason, it takes place within a society . Events and facts in society also affect the individual, who is a social being. Therefore, the society in which one lives shapes the individual. Due to this social impact, it may also have reflections on the individual as political reflection effects. These psychological effects that affect people's political participation can have two separate reflections: positive and negative psychological effects.

1.Positive psychological factors;

Positive Psychological Factors are generally factors that positively improve an individual's motivation and increase their participation. It is shaped as four factors: the individual's political interest, desire to engage in activity, social initiative and civic awareness. The first factor, Political interest; It is the attitude and action of a person towards political life in society. (Çadır, 2011: 19-20). Sense of political activity; It is the belief that the individual can influence decision-making processes in political events and organizations. (Akıncı, 2014: 313), The individual who increases his knowledge and equipment by participating in political processes

also gains self-confidence and self-worth. In this case, it increases the individual's desire to participate in more political events. (Altında, 2007: 51-53)

2.Negative psychological factors;

Negative Psychological Factors include factors that reduce the individual's participation in political events and political orders. Political Alienation can be shown as an example of these factors.

Political Alienation; It expresses the person 's lack of trust in the political organization (political system and political elements) in the society he is in. As a result of this distrust, the individual stays away from political events and does not participate or show support. (Altında, 2007: 54).

1.3.3.1.2. Gender Factor

The most important factor affecting political participation, which is the main subject of this study, is the (relative) gender factor.

Gender; The society in which the individual lives classifies the individual biologically. With this effect, a gender judgment is imposed on the entire sphere of life before it is born, and this is clearly reflected in the political perspective. Because, due to anatomic effects, society has already determined which professional fields individuals can work in, and women have had their share of this separation negatively. Women appear as a disadvantaged group in this separation. There is a belief that the male dominant class can carry out more political work and functions, which are generally pushed to the second position in all societies due to gender. The clearest indicator of this is that women, after men, have the right to vote and to be elected in our country, including all countries in the world (Çadır, 2011: 18-19). Baykal (1970: 63- 66). Even if a woman has a high level of education and a political inclination, she still has difficulty finding a place in the political organization, or even cannot find a place. The main reason for this is the perception of gender. Because the role of confining women to the home, such as housework and child rearing, has been defined from the beginning and this situation has been normalized by establishing a perception. This traditional role has also brought the woman to a submissive position behind her husband. Self-worth and self-respect are taught to

girls and boys from childhood, which hinders women's ability to assert themselves in the political arena. Therefore, the perception of gender and the gender roles it creates have always made women secondary, passive and submissive . It can be said that women have been negatively affected as a result of gender roles. (Kiziloluk , 1999: 223). Today's technological developments and global changes in almost every field are also evident in our country. Although this situation enables women to take a small place in business life , this is not at a sufficient level, and it is seen that a very minority of women are able to participate in the political field by overcoming the gender perception and the resulting gender roles. However, it is observed that women are still pushed into the background compared to men. Because, due to gender perception, while men are the main actors who can take part in politics, the perception that women are not sufficient in this field prevails and still continues. It can be said that gender roles are still an important obstacle for women in our country. Gender perception and, accordingly, gender roles are quite a factor in the reason why men have opportunities in almost every field, while women have obstacles in almost every field .

1.3.4. History of Political Participation in Turkey

in Turkey political to the past If we look at it , absolutism system with managed One regime first eye It crashes . Then first _political accession between 1876 and 1908 constitutionalism with has started . 1923 with the Republic political experience legal in process serious One enemy name in nature While counting , in the 1924 Constitution forces union principle and parliamentary system (to the parliament and parliament oppositeresponsible cabinet , subsequently the 1961 Constitution forces with _principle of separation (Legislative , Executive , Judicial) Democracy is also important from the steps It may end . Like this Parliament house - senate two- dimensional in the form One qualification won .

Freedom themewhat's that The resulting 1961 Constitution was oppressiveto the administrations about , political parties with civilians society to their organizations importance giving oppressive system balancing at the point important One enemy name in nature can be counted . Coup of 12 September 1980 post- 1982 Constitution double senate as required replaced by single party council to position has passed . forces separation principle in procedure to

stay together as one parliament system at the end politically your freedoms are increasingly restricted is seen . Political your participation- most important tool the one which... political of parties their freedom restricted , association , union with structures It was also cut between This Constitution with some political of parties shutting down to eye It crashes . For the 1982 Constitution , a kind of political life depoliticized was made can be said .

The phenomenon of politics and political processes in our country is a discipline that attracts the attention of many social scientists. Although it has had multi-party process experience for 78 years with the Republic (1946), it has not reached a political position at the international level. Although it is legally defined in our country that all individuals, both men and women, after the age of 18 can take part in the political arena , some invisible (glass ceiling syndrome) and visible (income, education, residence, country political conditions factor) obstacles do not offer people an equal track in terms of gender. While gender perception, gender roles and gender socialization can be considered as the main factors of Cam Taven syndrome, women are excluded from politics from birth and are raised away from politics since childhood. The fact that some women who overcome these obstacles do not have equal rights with men in the political arena changes women's interest in this field and directs it to different areas, so that women do not want to take part in politics of their own will. Obstacles that are likely to be encountered (housework, child care, etc. being expected from society and the spouse and the spouse's environment at the same time , the obstacle created by the perception that society is more suitable for men and the higher probability of society voting for men , the fact that women cannot make random decisions because they are fragile perception, the society's unwillingness to choose the woman due to the thought of separation or taking a break while the woman is pregnant, etc.) causes women to distance themselves from political decision-making processes and political activities. Society recognizes more roles for men as subjects in politics and classifies them as necessary . The fact that women actively have a say and participate is a level of access that casts a shadow over democracy in our country. However, a healthy social generation is only possible if both genders have a say. Because an indispensable element of a

democratic society is absolutely possible with the equal participation and access of both women and men.

1.4. Women's Status in Political Participation in the Context of Gender

1.4.1. Political Participation and Gender Relationship

Politics is society's ability to influence social areas with the participation of men and women, as a result of democracy. However, especially the patriarchal structure brings with it gender roles due to gender socialization and gender judgment roles. Due to these roles, women are not considered equal to men and are considered secondary. However, while democracy is defined as equality, especially in developing countries, women are always excluded from the political arena as a result of society's perception. We can state that the main reason why men do not have priority in political representation lies in the perception of gender, and accordingly, gender roles have a great impact. Because society has assigned certain roles to men and women before the individual is born, and stepping out of these roles can cause unseen difficulties. Glass ceiling syndrome can be defined as an invisible obstacle created by society . When we look at the roles that society assigns to women, there are many stereotypes such as being the lady of the house, raising children, giving, clothing, and areas where they can work , while the man is more interested in the livelihood of the house and his hunter nature is revealed. This gender factor, which excludes women from the working and political fields, is the main factor that keeps women in the background in terms of political representation in almost every country. However, while the nature of democracy emphasizes equality, the exclusion of women in political areas and their relegation to the background in political representation reveal that it is not compatible with the nature of democracy. (Yaylı and Eroğlu, 2015: 510-511). This situation brings about the inability to meet the equal needs of social layers and the failure to meet the desired development potential in society due to the unhappy woman factor.

1.4.2. Distribution of Political Representation by Gender

that in developed countries as well as developing countries, women are left behind in the political arena compared to men and are included in more disadvantaged groups . (Aydemir and Aydemir, 2011: 7). The factor that causes this

situation is the existence of a male-dominated perception rather than the reluctance of women. A patriarchal social structure, especially in developing countries, which is also true for our country, creates a class of women who are oppressed by social perceptions. The perception of male dominance in the patriarchal system, as well as gender-based restrictions on spatial , working and social areas, and gender-based restrictions on working conditions and areas, constantly push women to the background and exclude them. In social perception, women are described as naive, fragile, with low biological and cognitive skills, and are directly molded as unsuccessful as a result of gender classification. This pushes women to a secondary status as they grow up passive, have low self-worth and self-esteem, and grow up in line with these perceptions. In line with all these conclusions, women cannot show sufficient qualifications in the political field, and when they want to demonstrate, they are crushed under the perception of gender, due to the glass ceiling syndrome effect, which is not seen, and they start from behind in the political lane with men, and even if they are successful , a backward indicator appears due to the basic perception of gender perception. is coming out. (Berkday, 2006: 38). This situation may cause women who are excluded from politics or women who act with the anticipation of being excluded to display a reluctant attitude in the political arena compared to men. As a result of gender role socialization, the factors of the society in which the individual lives, and demographic variables such as economic, social, education, and marital status, gender discrimination in political orientation and politics occurs, and this situation becomes normal over time, again with the social factor. In this case, it is seen in the literature that it is expressed with gender role socialization. It can be said that societies appear to be a serious factor in an individual's professional orientation. Since men are considered to be in the upper class in the patriarchal structure, politics is seen as men's work. Due to the nature of political representation being a man's job, women are more pacified and are included in job descriptions such as housework, cooking and child care. Inferring from this, women automatically have a disadvantaged position in the political arena due to the gender socialization factor. (Gokulu , 2013: 351). Women do not have problems in office, not in being elected more, but in the electoral part of democracy, but they still face serious obstacles in terms of being elected compared to men. Being able to represent more politically means being excluded and at a disadvantage compared to

men in terms of political decision-making. (Örtlek and Tekelioğlu, 2013: 279). Gender roles, gender stereotypes and gender socialization factors, as in all societies, in our country, women's political representation is pushed to the background compared to men, and this causes men to have a monopoly in almost every field of political representation.

1.4.3. Gender Roles and Political Participation

Society One for both men and women set role definitions does. It's more gender features in line with this happening. Therefore, inside is located society cultural and faith values in line with both men and women norm quality of society called duty act according to definitions It does. developing the one which...our country inside This especially Woman in the context of male roles often heavy and oppressive. One attitude equality can show. Again Like our country, in Europe and America or Gender in Nigeria too aspect defined qualifications One eyelash If we throw it away, it's more rational, aggressive qualities such as initiative to eye multiplies. More houses make a living to provide whereas duty definitions between can be counted. Woman whereas again house like in our country chores, children growing, eating works, maintenance giver qualifications to eye multiplies. Passive, submissive it still happens One other qualities aspect can be counted. This perception with sleeping Individuals are also active like politics. fuck wanting or self-confidence and self-confidence value in jobs and tasks that require mostly place they couldn't get or preference what they didn't do is observed. Democracy from its nature incoming voting lots of activities outside undisclosed, political from the field far where they stand is observed. Here As can be seen, social gender judgments, gender Social roles such as socialization are very serious One active is seen. male profession aspect counted political trending activities again married for women your spouse preferred id political to structuring towards whereas One Another to eye multiplier is a finding. In the field in literature attention attracting One distinction is one in France is research. In this study, workers in the neighborhood residence who makes women bourgeois to class in proportion political vehicle in voting -most high in potential to be attention attracting One is detail. Another in literature to eye multiplier whereas women to politics the one which...their interests little is. Women made in research to scales given to the answers when

viewed high education in those who do including to be about given answers mostly to men “ I don't know ” or “ No answer ” statements compared to what's that is coming out .

1.4.4. Gender Roles, Women

Gender roles are divided into two parts in the literature . The first one is feminine, the other one is masculine. While society defines women's roles for feminine roles, it also defines men's roles for masculine. When we look at feminine roles, they are more passive, lacking in self-worth, obedient, sensitive, and care-giving, while masculine positions are more active, do not reflect their emotions, rational, fair, tough, have self-confidence and self-worth, strong, enterprising qualities. (Özcan, 2012: 12). . It is seen that gender roles are shaped mostly by the values and cultural judgments of the society in which the individual lives and the current time period. (Ökten, 2009: 303). Society expects the individual to fulfill certain coded qualities for both women and men, as there is a gender judgment pattern that defines and normalizes the roles that the individual will undertake according to the gender factor, and is often expected to do so. (Özcan, 2012: 10) The development level of the society is also important in shaping these roles. If an individual grows up in a traditional society, the woman is put in a disadvantaged position from the very beginning because she has a passive status according to the gender role template. It can be assumed that the patriarchal social construct ignores women in a way compared to men, by assigning women to the status of secondary existence. (Vefikuluçay et al., 2007: 27-28).

1.4.5. Women's Political Affairs In participation Location and Status

from the past to the present day women men with the equal to rights about struggles for many years is based on is seen . Developed in countries Woman Male to equality when we look at area aspect first we encountered education in the field equality to eye It crashes . Beginning in the 17th century equality with relating to concept 18th and 19th century with one more importance won and won in 1776 published in American Freedom Declaration with won rights later in 1789 _French Humanity and Citizenship Rights Declaration with legal aspect is defined is seen . In this

phase industrialization serious enemy name While , with the capitalist system of states nationalization in the process idealized political and economic improvements gender inequality serious changes along with brought . Moreover in America and France revolutions and societies on freedom of perception in adoption serious at a rate effect undeniable . (Quoted by Jaggar , Sallan Gül, 2003). emergence coming out freedom , intellectual approaches , women in every field political as it is in the field promise ownerto be able to be and to be able to receive active has happened . The first of these voting , woman _ _ political in the field promise able to take place to be able to acquire in the name of important enemy name aspect can be qualified .

1.4.6. Women in Turkey Political Participation

in Turkey women in the west women's social rights to win with when compared west women at the base bus movements in line with to rights and struggles own they are to eye it crashes . we have whereas Ottoman during periods women association through with for rights and struggle they started is observed . in 1923 women established is The association later became known as the " Women's People's Party " . in the form of a political party one to the structure But in that period to the constitution against to be found with closed shut down this party to 1934 _ much women political in structure cannot be positioned is seen .

made constitutional with change finally the year 1934 with Voting and election for women right has been given . This change 18 women in line deputy in parliament place found it . from the past to the present day when viewed most high woman rate in parliament Considering the Turkish Grand National Assembly Fifth council aspect can be said . 4.6% in this parliament woman in parliament representation right won is seen . made analyzes When examined, the years between 1935 and 2002 between women general aspect in parliament positions 4.6% to 4.4 % is seen and it is to men how much compared to back that it is apparent indicator aspect can be seen . from the Ottoman This sideways women to your problems immediately immediately most council group As he didn't mention, he 's always dualist . in the background is evaluated can be said . women in parliament to their locations when viewed of numbers scarcity next to you , word own the one which... women are also masculine role pattern their

adoption attention attracting One other is the situation . Social pattern judgment even today still masculine vocational group in is evaluated Woman concept Woman Concepts such as representation are all or nothing is counted or second _in the background is evaluated is observed .

in Turkey social gender pattern To what extent are their judgments raised with the equivalent at a rate women are also political on the platform place received can be said . Another _expression with woman life within and political in the field How positioned , women are political to the lane in their orientation effective the one which...-most big active aspect still effective the one which...social gender roles , society from the past since ongoing imposed by social gender judgment molds with women political participation in under the influence important is considered .

1.4.7. The Necessity of Women's Representation in Politics

If we are talking about an egalitarian society, and considering that individuals in this society will be men and women due to their gender, it is a necessity of democracy that women and men have equal rights. If we cannot talk about an egalitarian society without women's right to speak and act, it is unthinkable to use the expression of an egalitarian society without men. Equality indicates that women and men have equal say and action rights in terms of decision, attitude and action. Any field where only male dominance prevails and where only men have the right to speak and act brings with it absolute deficiency. Because in an egalitarian society, there are not only men. Conversely, in societies where only women have the right to speak and act, we cannot talk about the absolutely adequate representation of men, and here, due to the lack of adequate representation, the party with insufficient representation will definitely not be able to access their adequate rights. This will lead to an unhappy individual and, as a result, an unhappy society. If there is a completely fair expression of democracy, this society ensures that both men and women can be in a fair position and on equal platforms in every field. This can lead to a society that thrives on health. It can be said that in developed societies, men and women can take part in any field they want as a result of an equal distribution of labor and capital. The main factor here is women's ability to take part in decision-

making centers and representation equally, as a result of equal opportunities, in the political arena as well as in every field. In other words, it can be said that this equal gender approach in the political arena is a necessity rather than a blessing.

Politics is considered a male profession in our country. As a result of this gendering in the profession, the subject of politics is constructed as male . In the political field, in this case, men take an active role in politics, men should only be the decision-making mechanism , the stereotype that men should only be good, successful and successful in representation prevails. The male-dominated professional tendency resulting from this social professional gendering completely excludes women. He even ignores it (Terkan , 2010: 121). However, women continue to exist as a number in that society, and even when compared to the proportion of men, there are more women than men in our country, this discrimination reveals a complete injustice. If we think that a woman understands a woman best, it is obvious how successful a man can be in determining all the needs of a woman and eliminating this deficiency. In addition, polyphony and multicoloration bring success and development as a reflection of different perspectives in the political field, as in every field. The common conclusion of all these determinations can be expressed as the absolute presence of women in all processes of politics (decision-making, selection, election, representation, etc.), as they are at least as high a representation as men in every field and especially in all decision-making centers of the country . a need is a necessity. The modern world order is possible with contemporary approaches. In this situation, the fact that both men and women can take part in equal and fair representation in the political arena may be a result of the natural creation of this situation. It can be said that the existence of happy, productive, developmentally open and different perspectives is possible with equal gender representation, and this is a right and an obligation.

1. 4.8. Map of Women in Political Life

1.4.8.1. The Place and Status of Women in Political Life - World

the 2023 IPU (Inter-Parliamentary Union)-UN (United Nations Women's Unit) Women 2023 map data, it was observed that although more women took part in

decision-making processes in the political arena around the world compared to previous years, gender equality was still not achieved.

The published map (January 1, 2023) includes women's managerial status and current values in the national political arena. According to these values, although there is an increase in the number of women in political leadership positions in government and parliament all over the world, these numbers are still quite low in some countries.

According to the 'Women in Politics 2023' map outputs;

The List of Women in the highest offices of state (Figure 1) is presented below.

Figure 1: List of Women in the highest positions of state

Source: turkiye.un.org(2023)

<u>1 January 2014</u>	<u>1 January 2023</u>
Head of Government Female: 7.3%	9.8%
Female Head of State: 5.3%	11.3%

the research data of the "2023 Women in Political Life Map", which includes 193 countries, is examined, according to the data of January 1, 2023, 9.8% of the

heads of government are women (19 of 193 countries) and 11.3% of the heads of state are women who have a say in the political arena. It has been observed that . When we look at the general result of the data, it shows that the European country is and continues to be the country where women continue to have the most say in the political arena.

The List of World and Regional Averages for Women in Parliament (Figure 2) is presented below.

	Tek meclis veya alt meclis	Üst meclis veya Senato	Her iki meclis birleşik
Dünya ortalaması	%26,5	%26,1	%26,5
Bölgesel ortalamalar			
<small>Bölgeler, tek meclisli parlamentolardaki veya alt meclisteki kadınların oranına göre azalan biçimde sıralanmıştır.</small>			
İskandinav ülkeleri	%45,7	—	—
Amerika kıtası	%34,9	%34,6	%34,9
Avrupa (İskandinav ülkeleri dâhil)	%31,1	%30,7	%31,0
Europe (İskandinav ülkeleri hariç)	%29,5	%30,7	%29,8
Sahraaltı Afrika	%26,6	%26,1	%26,5
Asya	%21,2	%19,4	%21,0
Pasifik	%19,5	%49,4	%22,6
Orta Doğu ve Kuzey Afrika	%17,7	%11,3	%16,3

*PAB bölgesel gruptandırma derlemesine şu adresten erişilebilir: <https://data.ipu.org/content/regional-groupings>.

Figure 2: List of World and Regional Averages for Women in Parliament

Source: turkiye.un.org(2023)

2021 January 1, 2023

Female Members of Parliament worldwide: 25.5% 26.5%

Female Speaker in Parliament: 20.9% 22.7%

It has been observed that the rate of Women Speakers of Parliament in Parliament worldwide in 2021 increased from 20.9% to 22.7% on January 1, 2023, and the rate of Women Members of Parliament worldwide increased from 25.5% to 26.5%.

January 1, 2023

Ratio of Female Ministers in the World: 22.8%

Countries with a female ratio in the Ministerial Cabinet:

Europe - North America : 31.6%

Latin America and the Caribbean: 30.1%

Central Asia and South Asia : 10.1%

Pacific Islands : 8.1%

January 1, 2023 According to Women in Politics 2023 data, the rate of female ministers among the world countries is 22.8%, while Europe and North America take the first place in the list of countries with the highest proportion of women in the ministerial cabinet in the Parliament with 31.6%, followed by 30%. Latin America and the Caribbean with a rate of 1, Central Asia and South Asia with 10.1%, and the Pacific Islands with 8.1% are among the countries with the lowest female ministerial representatives.

The List of Fields Where Women Ministers Work is presented below (Figure 3).

Figure 3: List of Fields Where Women Ministers Work
Source: turkiye.un.org(2023)

Another data revealed in the 2023 Women's Political Study is that when we look at the fields where female ministers work, it is seen that they work in the Ministry of Environment with a rate of 32%, in the Ministry of Public Administration with a rate of 30%, and in the ministries of education with a rate of

30% . When we look at gender equality, it can be said that the data obtained is far behind compared to men and this situation still continues.

Sima Bahous (2023), Executive Director of Un Women, as follows: 'This data shows us that women are not adequately represented at the head of state or government levels. While less than a quarter of ministries are held by women, men continue to dominate ministries such as economy, defense and energy. Full democracy can only be achieved with the equal participation of women. Ongoing violence and threats against women leaders prevent candidates and voters from speaking out about the need for economic and social recovery. We really need a change that will ensure equality.'(turkiye.un.org, 2023)

IPU Secretary General Martin Chungong (2023) as follows: 'We are encouraged to observe an increase in the number of women in politics this year. However, current growth rates show that we still have a long way to go to achieve gender equality. In order to solve problems such as climate change crises, geopolitical tensions, economic instability and social inequality, women's talents need to be better evaluated and their participation in politics should be encouraged.'(turkiye.un.org, 2023)

It can be stated with inferences from the research data titled 2023 Women in Politics: 2023, which is the research data conducted by the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) and the United Nations Women's Unit, that although the expression of gender equality is used, women cannot have enough say in the political field in all countries of the world. It is observed around the world that women are quite inadequate in decision-making processes in the political arena. In 31 countries, women serve as either Heads of State or Heads of Government, 26.5% are among the members of Parliament, and 22.8% are among the cabinet ministers worldwide, which is less than a quarter of the cabinet ministers worldwide. It turns out that women, as well as men, dominate the political arena throughout the world, and we can state that gender equality is very much in question in this case.

1. 4.8.2. The Place and Status of Women in Political Life – Turkey

The "Women in Politics 2023" map printouts also include data for Türkiye. One of the prominent data in the study is the quota application. As a requirement of the multi-party parliament, which is indispensable for democracy, political parties take precautions to pave the way for a certain amount of female candidates to take part in the political field. Here, it can be seen that it creates space for female candidates to take part in the political arena and also gives them the rankings they can achieve in order to win. It can be said that parties set gender quotas when creating their candidates and open a certain proportion of the number of candidates to women's applications.

the household labor force survey conducted by YSK in 2022 regarding working life, according to the employment rate of those aged 15 and over, 30.4% of women are in working life, while this rate is 65.00% of men. Again, when the labor force participation rate is examined, according to the same research results, while the labor force participation rate for women is 35.1%, the labor force participation rate for men is 71.4%. It can be seen that women are less than half as active in working life as men. In the political lane, this rate decreases and it can be stated according to the following data outputs that the masculine structuring in the political lane is more masculine than the rate in working life .

The results of the research conducted by YSK in 2022 are presented in the form of tables below.

The List of the Number of Women Members of Parliament between 2013 and 2022 is given below (Figure 4).

Figure 4: List of the Number of Women Members of Parliament
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

YSK 's periodic _conducts analyses . According to the data output of the Number of Women Deputies comparing the years 2022 and 2013, which is one of the analyzes that also includes comparison data by years, it is seen that only 100 of the 577 Deputies in the Turkish Grand National Assembly in 2022 are women deputies. When the table is examined, while there were 104 female MPs in 2018, the number gradually decreased and decreased to 100 in 2022.

TURKISH GRAND NATIONAL ASSEMBLY. The Number of Women Members of Parliament for the 27th Term is presented below (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Grand National Assembly of Turkey. List of Number of Women Members of Parliament in the 27th Term
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

TURKISH GRAND NATIONAL ASSEMBLY. Looking at the number of female and male deputies of political parties in the 27th Term, the number of deputies of the Justice and Development Party (AKP) is 285, of which 54 are female deputies. Again, the number of deputies of the Republican People's Party (CHP) is 134, and 16 of this number are female deputies. HDP has 56 deputies, 22 of which are women deputies. The research findings show that while the Nationalist Movement Party (MHP) has 4 female deputies with 48 seats, and the İyi Party has 37 seats, this number is 2 female deputies.

The List of the Number of Women Ministers between 2002 and 2022 is presented below (Figure 6).

Figure 6: List of the Number of Women Ministers between 2002 and 2022
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

As seen in the table above, the number of female ministers is considerably lower than that of men. The ministry that appeared in the last Parliament was the "Ministry of Family and Social Policies" and it is seen that there was a female minister serving.

The List of the Number of Women Ambassadors between 2010 and 2022 is presented below (Figure 7).

Figure 7: List of the Number of Female Ambassadors between 2010 and 2022
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

As seen in the table above, the number of female ambassadors is also significantly lower than that of men. According to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs study, the female ambassador rate in 2011 was 11.9%, and this rate will be 27.2% in 2022.

The List of the Number of Female District Governors between 2010 and 2022 is presented below (Figure 8).

Figure 8: List of the Number of Female District Governors between 2010 and 2022
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

of YSK is examined, there is an increase compared to the years, but there is a decrease in the number in 2022 (26) compared to the previous year (38).

The List of the Number of Women Council Members between 2004 and 2022 is presented below (Figure 9).

Figure 9: List of the Number of Women Council Members between 2004 and 2022
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

As seen above, in the study conducted, it is revealed that while there was 1 council member in 2004, there were no women in the number of council members in 14 years, and according to the results of the last research in the following years and in 2022, 2 council members were women.

The List of the Number of Women Governors between 2010 and 2022 is presented below (Figure 10).

Figure 10: List of the Number of Female Governors between 2010 and 2022
Source: verikaynagi.com (2022)

by YSK is examined, it can be said that the proportion of men is high. The number of governors in 2022 is 2, and as a general result of all data, it can be stated that the masculine structuring is still actively continuing in our country.

SECOND PART

In this section, the purpose of the research, its importance, problem statement, sub-problems, hypotheses, assumptions and limitations of the research, methods and techniques of the research, procedure, statistical analysis and validity and reliability are included.

2. METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

2.1. Purpose of the research

The aim of this research is to determine the relationship between the attitudes of 4th grade adolescents studying at the high school level towards the political representation of women in Turkey in the context of gender, the role of gender roles on the political representation of women and social phobia. In this study, 3 different types of high schools (Vocational High School, Science High School and Imam Hatip High School) were collected within the framework of volunteering with the maximum diversity sampling method, among the students who were educated in secondary schools in state institutions affiliated with the Ministry of National Education within the borders of Çankaya, Etimesgut and Sincan districts of Ankara province.) male and female students from each type of school were determined as samples. It is aimed to conduct a comprehensive study examining the attitudes of these students towards women's political representation in Turkey and how they differ according to gender roles and the relationship between this situation and social anxiety.

2.2. Importance of Research

Social anxiety is a mood disorder in which an individual feels anxious and worried about being criticized or humiliated by others in social environments. Although this disorder occurs in a small amount in every individual, this rate can be disturbing in some individuals. As a result of this situation, the individual may sometimes face problems in his/her career life and sometimes in communication with family/social ties. Although there are many individuals who are faced with the

problems caused by this situation, it is observed that there is a negligible scarcity in the literature in our country regarding the field or a study that provides complete treatment. It is obvious that the existence of healthier, more functional, more self-confident and self-worth individuals and a more productive society will be achieved through research on the treatment of social anxiety (phobia) individuals experiencing social anxiety. For this reason, it is thought that this study to be conducted with individuals will contribute to both the field and the field.

Since this study is the first to examine the attitudes of 17-year-old adolescents, who are before the voting age, towards women's political representation, taking into account both their relationship with family, economic, cultural, education and career, the role of gender roles in this context, and their correlation with social phobia. It is thought to be a study of high scientific originality and contribution to the literature. In addition, a personal information form and a socio -demographic diagnostic form developed by the researcher himself in the context of the students' age, socio -economic level, parents' educational status , are important for the study as it is a research to be examined in the context of differences caused by regional, educational-cultural-economic etc. variables. It is thought to be. In addition, it is thought that this research is important in knowing the perspectives of adolescents, revealing the obstacles to the infrastructure of minority female representatives in our country and solving these obstacles. Although it is not a sufficient variable to consider society's attitudes towards gender roles alone, considering the individual's self-confidence, self-worth and social phobia variables together will result in individuals growing up today being more self-confident, their self-worth and social anxiety levels are minimized, and their social self-esteem is It is thought that this research is important for the emergence of female individuals who express themselves. It is observed that women's political roles in the context of gender are not at a sufficient level in our country, and it is thought to be important to determine the relationship between the adolescents' perspective and social phobia, which is thought to be among the reasons for this situation. In addition, according to the indicators emerging as a result of the research, it is thought that the determination of suggestions to increase the role of women in politics may be useful both for

researchers working in the field and for female politicians who are actively involved in the field and who are considering taking an active role . this thesis

2.3. Problem Statement, Sub-Problems

2.3.1. Problem Sentence;

“According to the opinions of 17-year-old adolescents (senior high school) who are before the voting age, is there a relationship between their attitudes towards women's political representations in the context of gender and social anxiety (social phobia)? It was determined as “.

2.3.2. Sub-Problems of the Research

Within the scope of the study, answers are sought to the following problem statements:

1. a. Do the effects of demographic characteristics on Social Anxiety differ for adolescents (according to gender, income level, education level, age status, parental culture/marriage bond, age/education, high school type and regional differences)? How?
adolescents , does it create a difference in their views on women's representations regarding career choice tendencies according to gender, income level, regional differences, school type? How?
2. Does the level of Social Anxiety differ according to Social Relationship and Performance, which are the sub-dimensions of demographic characteristics for adolescents (gender, income level, education level, regional difference, age status, parental culture/marriage bond, age/education, school type status)? From where?
3. What are the opinions of senior high school students regarding the political representation of women in Turkey? How?
4. Is there a relationship between women's political representation and social phobia among female and male high school senior students? How?
5. a. Do the attitudes of male and female high school senior students towards women's managerial representations and their intentions for political representations differ significantly? How? From where?

- b. Do women's attitudes towards political representation and, in the context of women's managerial tendencies, significantly predict their intentions? How?
6. If you were to compare the concept of "women's management representation" in Turkey to something, what would you compare it to? From where?

2.4. Hypotheses (Hypotheses)

1. positive significant relationship between 17-year-old adolescents' attitude towards women's political representation in Turkey and its relationship with social anxiety in the context of gender perception.
2. between 17-year-old adolescents' attitudes towards women's political representation in Turkey and their relationship with social anxiety in the context of gender perception.
3. Attitudes of 17-year-old adolescents towards the political representation of women in Turkey, education level / social perception , regional situations, economic situations , etc. According to their socio -demographic status, women's political representation intentions differ at a positive and significant level.
4. Attitudes of 17-year-old adolescents towards the political representation of women in Turkey, education level / social perception , regional situations, economic situations , etc. According to their socio -demographic status, women's political representation intentions differ at a negatively significant level.
5. Attitudes of 17-year-old adolescents towards the political representation of women in Turkey, education level/social perception, regional situations, economic situations, etc.It varies significantly according to the intention towards gender perception according to socio -demographic situations.
6. There is/is no significant relationship between 17-year-old adolescents' attitudes towards women's political representation and social anxiety.
7. Social Anxiety Scale for Adolescents varies according to gender, income-education, age, regional and school type.

8. The sub-dimensions of the Social Anxiety Scale for Adolescents (Social Relationship and Performance) differ according to gender, income-education, age, regional and school type.
9. Gender Perception Scale differs according to gender, income-education, age, regional and school type.
10. Gender Perception Scale differs according to its sub-dimensions (family education-income level, regional), gender, income-education, age, regional and school type.

2.5. Assumptions of the Research

1. The participants in the study answered the questions included in each scale impartially and sincerely.
2. the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale to measure the sample's attitudes towards social anxiety and the "Gender Perception Scale" to measure Gender Perception attitudes are reliable and valid measurement tools.
3. It is assumed that the individuals constituting the sample of the research represent the universe.
4. It measures the variables related to the "Social Anxiety Scale for Adolescents" and "Gender Perception Scale" used in the research as valid and safe.

2.6. Limitations of the Research

1. The findings obtained from the research will be limited to the universe represented by the determined sample.
2. Social desirability error may be confounded due to the use of a self-report style scale in the study.
3. Due to the design of the research, it is not possible to establish a cause-effect relationship between the variables and to make longitudinal inferences.
4. The population of the research is limited to adolescent individuals aged 17 years old residing in Ankara province, Çankaya, Sincan and Etimesgut districts.
5. The sample of the research consists of randomly selected individuals aged 17 and who agreed to participate in our research.

6. The variables examined in the study are limited to the characteristics measured by the " Socio -Demographic - Personal Information Form", "Gender Perception Scale" and " Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale" and individual interview forms used in the research and developed by the researcher.
7. The research results can only be generalized to those who have similar personal and demographic information to the individuals participating in the research.

2.7. of researchMethods and Techniques

In this section, information is given about the research model, population, sample, study group, data collection tools, data collection and data analysis methods.

2. 7.1 Model of the Research

This research is a mixed method research and is a study with a convergent parallel design. Here, quantitative and qualitative data are of equal importance, and data is collected either sequentially or in equal parallel, depending on demand. Subsequently, they are analyzed separately and the data obtained are interpreted together in the interpretation section. Creswell (2003) stated that there are many different levels of techniques and methods in research, which may cause confusion for researchers during the study, so a new method is needed. Mixed method is a study that is more of a mixture of quantitative and qualitative (Creswell, 2003; Tashakkori and Teddlie , 1998; Johnson and Onwuegbuzie , 2004). According to Creswell (2006), conducting only qualitative or quantitative research studies opens a one-dimensional window into the existing problem . However, he states that in a comparative study, both qualitative and quantitative, more reliable results can be achieved if the problem is multidimensional.

Figure 1. Converging Parallel Pattern

2.7.2. Universe of Research

The research was conducted in the 2023-2024 academic year of adolescent students aged 17 years old (12th grade), corresponding to the age before the voting age, who are studying in institutions affiliated with the Ministry of Education in Çankaya, Sincan and Etimesgut districts of Ankara province, and studying in different types of schools: Vocational High School - Imam Hatip High School and Science High School. consists of students.

2.7.3. Sample of the Research

The sample of this research was chosen as sequential and simultaneous mixed method sampling. Sequential and simultaneous Mixed Method Sampling is the most preferred method because it is the most convenient method for the researcher in mixed design (Creswell, Plano Clark, Gutmann , & Hanson, 2003; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie , 2004). Another convenience factor that is a factor in the choice of Sequential and Simultaneous Mixed Method sampling is that both the probability sampling method can be selected sequentially as Quantitative-Qualitative or Qualitative-Quantitative, and the purposeful sampling method can be preferred together. This method provides the convenience of collecting data both qualitatively and quantitatively, alternately or simultaneously, or separately and sequentially. Combining the data obtained in a study allows the findings to be verified, supported or cross-validated. In the simultaneous transformational sampling method, quantitative and qualitative data are collected together, analyzed separately, and

combined and interpreted with equal importance during the interpretation of the data. Thus, it allows alternative perspectives and supports the study problem statement.

For the sample of the research, students attending Science High School,

Code	Gender	School Region	School Type	Family Education	Number of Siblings	Parental Status
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Vocational High School and Imam Hatip High School from three districts were determined, and 35 percent of the sample was reached from these three determined regions . This number is sufficient for research.

2.7.4 Working Group of the Research

For the qualitative part of the research, nested multiple case design was preferred among case study designs , and easily accessible sampling method, one of the purposeful sampling methods, was chosen as the sample. In this context, 12 student participants, one female and one male student each, studying in 3 school types determined as randomly and easily accessible to represent the universe of the research being educated in public schools in the 2023/2024 academic year in Sincan, Etimesgut and Çankaya districts of Ankara Province, were participated on a voluntary basis. was included in the research. The table showing the demographic characteristics of the study group is presented in Table 1.

Table1. Study Group Demographic Characteristics Table

K1	MALE	ÇANKAYA	SCIENCE HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: LICENSE FATHER: LICENSE	one	SEPARATE
K2	WOMAN	ÇANKAYA	SCIENCE HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: LICENSE FATHER: PhD	one	SEPARATE
K3	WOMAN	ÇANKAYA	IMAM HATIP	MOTHER: LICENSE FATHER: LICENSE	one	SEPARATE
K4	WOMAN	ETİMESGUT	SCIENCE HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: LOAD. LICENCE FATHER: HIGH SCHOOL	-	TOGETHER
K5	MALE	ETİMESGUT	SCIENCE HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: HIGH SCHOOL FATHER: LICENSE	one	TOGETHER
K6	WOMAN	ETİMESGUT	VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: PRIMARY SCHOOL FATHER: PRIMARY SCHOOL	-	TOGETHER
K7	MALE	XINJAN	SCIENCE HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: HIGH SCHOOL FATHER: LICENSE	-	TOGETHER
K8	MALE	XINJAN	IMAM HATIP	MOTHER: PRIMARY SCHOOL FATHER: PRIMARY SCHOOL	4	TOGETHER
K9	WOMAN	XINJAN	IMAM HATIP	MOTHER: HIGH SCHOOL FATHER: MIDDLE SCHOOL	2	TOGETHER
K10	WOMAN	ETİMESGUT	IMAM HATIP	MOTHER: HIGH SCHOOL FATHER: LICENSE	-	SEPARATE
K11	WOMAN	ÇANKAYA	VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: LICENSE FATHER: LICENSE	-	SEPARATE
K12	WOMAN	XINJAN	VOCATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL	MOTHER: HIGH SCHOOL FATHER: HIGH SCHOOL	2	TOGETHER

2.7.5 Data Collection Tools

the Socio Demographic Personal Information Form developed by the researcher ,

For the Qualitative Part of the Research;

2.7.5.1 Informed Consent Form

Before the research process, St. This form, which was approved by the Clements University Ethics Committee, was subsequently approved by the Ankara Provincial Directorate of National Education Ethics Committee in order to be applied to participants at the secondary education level within the Ministry of National Education. In line with the permissions obtained, detailed information about the content and purposes of the research was given to the participating adolescents and

their parents. On a voluntary basis and in accordance with the principle of confidentiality, detailed information was shared, including the interview processes and that no names would be used and transfer would be made through coding. If the participants agreed to participate in the study after learning this information, their signatures were taken on this form indicating that they participated in the study voluntarily .

2.7.5.2 Socio -demographic Information Form, Fully Structured Interview Questions and Semi-Structured Individual Interview Form Questions

Semi-Structured Individual Interview Form was used. The form was developed by the researcher. The form is organized in 3 parts. In the first part, 14 questions include personal demographic questions about the participant (age, gender, marital status, education level, father's education level, mother's education level, etc.). Then, in the second part, as Semi-Structured Interview Questions, participants' individual characteristics (enterprising, assertive, Should there be studies on women's social lives with questions that determine questions such as: shy , active, do I have/don't have self-worth, etc. ? Shouldn't it work? In which areas should he work? Questions, again signs containing the questions "If women should work , why?" and "If they should not work, why?" and questions containing open-ended answers in the blank, Are women successful in politics? From where? Do they fail? There are Part 2 questions in the form of marking that include why questions. In the third part, which is the last part, 6 questions and the answers to these questions are arranged in an open-ended manner regarding the relationship between Women's political representation and Social Anxiety in the Context of Gender, which is the main theme of the study. The last question to the participants was "If you were to compare the concept of "women's management representation" in Turkey to something, what would you compare it to?" From where?" The question is a purely metaphorical question and was directed to the participants.

For the quantitative part of the research;

2.7.5.3 Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS)

Original name: Liebowitz Social anxiety The form, which is the scale , was created by Liebowitz in 1987 and was developed by Heimberg , Horner , Juster , Safren and

their colleagues in 1999 with validity and reliability studies. The purpose of the scale is to measure the fear and anxiety levels of individuals suffering from social anxiety disorder due to anxiety in society during social communication situations or when they need to perform . The scale, consisting of 24 items, has two dimensions: social interaction (11) and performance (13) . The items of the scale are in the form of a four-point Likert and each is evaluated separately under the headings of anxiety and avoidance. The patient marks the scale and performs the filling function. Finally, the scores obtained from all items are summed. The Turkish version of the scale does not include a cut-off score. Turkish versions of the scale were published by Soykan et al. (2003) and Dilbaz, (2001). It is a scale generally applied by individuals who have knowledge of psychopathology . However, since the scale can show reliable and valid results for self-report purposes, it can also be applied to healthy individuals for screening purposes. (Fresco , Coles , Heimberg , Liebowitz et al., 2001). The Cronbach's alpha value of the scale can vary between .81 and .92. (Heimberg et al., 1999)

2.7.5.4 Gender Perception Scale

The Gender Perception Scale, developed by Altinova and Duyan (2013) to measure individuals' gender perceptions, consists of a total of 25 items. 10 of the items were written as positive and 15 as negative. The scale was adapted as a five-point Likert , which includes the determination of perspectives as "I completely agree (5), I agree (4), I am undecided (3), I disagree (2), I completely disagree (1) . As the scores increase, it shows that Gender Perception is at an appropriate and positive level. (Altinova and Duyan, 2013). The score that can be obtained from the total scale is between 25 and 125, and it is a one-dimensional scale according to the explanatory factor analysis data output for the validity of the scale. For the reliability of the scale, the Cronbach Alpha value was found to be 0.872 and thus the alpha reliability coefficient was determined to be at the level.

2.7.6 Data Collection Method of the Research

For the quantitative part of the research;

In this study, data were collected from students by applying the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale and the Gender Perception Scale developed by

Altınova and Duyan (2013). The package program used for data analysis is SPSS 22.0 Statistics program.

For the qualitative part of the research;

For the qualitative part of the research, the socio -demographic information of the students was collected with the Socio -Demographic Personal Information Form, Fully Structured Interview Form and Semi-Structured Interview Form developed by the researcher .

2.8.Transaction

Before the data collection process, St. After Ethics Committee permissions were obtained from Clements University and Ankara MEB Provincial Directorate of National Education,

For the quantitative part of the research;

1. Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale
2. Gender Perception Scale

It was applied via online Google Form.

Within the scope of the research, first of all, the aim of the research was to use the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale and the Gender Perception Scale developed by Altınova and Duyan (2013) for the 2023-2024 academic year, among high school senior adolescents in Çankaya, Sincan and Etimesgut districts of Ankara Province, to students who volunteered to participate in the research. It was applied by providing a link to the scales created in the form of a Google Online Form. Subsequently, the data obtained was analyzed with the support of SPSS 11 package program.

For the Qualitative Part of the Research;

For research in St. Following the permission approval of the Slements University Ethics Committee, permission was obtained from the Ankara Provincial Directorate of National Education Ethics Committee. Subsequently, the participants who want to participate in our research on a voluntary basis among high school

senior adolescents in Çankaya, Sincan and Etimesgut districts of Ankara province in the 2023-2024 academic year are respectively;

1. Informed Consent Form,
2. Socio -demographic Information Form developed by the researcher ,
3. Full and Semi-Structured Individual Interview Form

Its application has been made .

The Socio- demographic form , which was developed by the researcher personally after signing the informed consent form, consists of 3 parts. In the Personal information section, which contains personal information about the participant, information such as name and student number that would reveal the identity of the students was never requested and the necessary warning was made in the explanation section. After the first part in the form of marking , the second part in the form of blanks, open-ended questions and marking included questions about the participant's individual characteristics (anxious, passive, self-esteem, etc.) and the courses he/she liked/disliked at school and their reasons. In the last part, which covers the theme of the research and consists of fill-in-the-blank, open-ended answers and markings, questions are included, such as the reasons for the success/failure of women in politics, should women work? Should they not work? In which professions should women work? This form was delivered to the participants face to face , online Zoom or in word via WhatsApp, depending on availability, and the form was made ready for analysis after they filled it out. Finally, the main theme of the research, which includes the relationship between women's perception of gender in the context of social anxiety and open-ended questions, was prepared before the open-ended questions by an expert in the field and with the researcher, and interviews were conducted one- on- one or via online zoom , in line with the permission obtained from the participants who participated in the research on a voluntary basis . The interviews were transferred to the computer environment via verbatim transcription . The data obtained was then transferred to the Nvivo package program and themed . Afterwards, descriptive analysis was carried out.

2.9. Calendar and Manpower

Theoretical Research (Literature Review):

15.10.2023-11.01.2024

Obtaining Necessary Permissions:

01.11. 2023-20.11.2023

Analysis Process

Data Collection and Analysis (Experimental Research):

20.11.2023-05.01.2024

Preparation and Presentation of the Project:

05.01.2024-26.01.2024

2. 10.Data Collection, Analysis and Conclusion

Collecting Data
Analysis of Data
Raw Data / Groups
Data Reduction
Configuring Sections
Original Data Analysis
Presentation of Findings
Drawing Conclusions
Final Report

Figure 11: Data Collection, Analysis and Conclusion (Çukadar and Çelik, 2003)

2.11. Project Work-Timeline

Table 2. Project Work-Timeline

Months	October 2023	November 2023	December 2023	January 2024
Source Browsing	X	X	X	X

ScaleDevelopment	X	X	X	
of the methodWriting	X	X	X	
of scaleImplementation		x	x	x
ResearchReport			x	x
Researchof the reportdelivery				x

2.12. Statistical Analysis

For the quantitative part of the research;

The data obtained as a result of the research were first entered into the Statistical Package Program for Social Sciences SPSS.22 program in a controlled manner. Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the relationship between the answers given by male and female 17-year-old high school senior adolescent students to the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale and the Gender Perception Scale developed by Altınova and Duyan (2013) .

For the qualitative part of the research;

For the qualitative part of the research, the data obtained from the individual interview form was transferred to the computer without any changes and then analyzed in the Nvivo 12 package program. First of all, the individual interviews were transferred to the computer environment without any changes, and the resulting transcripts were themed by experts in the field with the support of the package program . The resulting themes were subjected to descriptive analysis. Subsequently, the results were subjected to kappa analysis.

2.13. Validity Reliability

In qualitative studies, "validity" refers to the accuracy of scientifically obtained findings, while "reliability" refers to the scientific findings reaching the same conclusion every time. In order to achieve this, the participants were allowed to participate in the study in line with their consent and scales were used. The validity of the findings and data obtained is interpreted as the accuracy and perfection of the study . The power of a qualitative study that includes the problem statement of a

study-oriented research, the research process, a group within the community, or a related phenomenon, concept or model expresses the validity of that study . Repeating the results repeatedly and reaching the same result includes the consistency of the study, and at the same time, the ability of the sample used in the research to accurately represent the universe is described as "reliability" (Joppe , 2000). In this context, the group of the study is high school senior adolescents in Çankaya, Sincan and Etimesgut districts of Ankara . The mass was selected and assumed to represent the total universe. Additionally, participants' consent was obtained. Thus, validity and reliability were ensured. In order to increase reliability in the research, semi-structured interview form questions were prepared with expert support. In line with the permissions obtained, the interview was held face to face or via Zoom , where possible, and the recording process was carried out at the same time. The recording is transcribed verbatim , without any additions or deletions, by transferring it to the computer environment. It was translated and parent themes were created by experts in the field with the support of NVIVO 11 Package Program. Following the data obtained , descriptive analysis was performed. Again, to increase credibility, if you wanted to compare the concept of "women's political representation" in the context of gender to something, what would you compare it to? From where? A metaphor question such as " was asked to the participants. In line with these data, the validity and reliability of the research was ensured.

Within the scope of the credibility of the study, in order to have a high internal validity value, Semi-Structured Interview Form Questions prepared by the researcher with expert support in the field, Socio -Demographic Interview Form Questions consisting of three qualified parts to support the study, and Semi-Structured Interview Questions containing open-ended answers were prepared and in accordance with the National Education Legislation. The study was supported as qualitative data collection tools with documents added to the study in line with its suitability . The applicability of the forms was carried out by the researcher on a voluntary basis, face to face and via online zoom , with easy accessibility technique . Subsequently, the data obtained and the results obtained were evaluated comparatively. On the other hand, the participants were asked to sign a consent form, which included information at the beginning, and they were informed about the confidentiality of the study and that a coding method would be used instead of name

and surname. Again, signing an agreement stating that the information recorded during online and face-to-face meetings will be used only for scientific purposes and that it is confidential is an important factor in ensuring mutual trust. These processing processes show that it can be stated that the collection and process of the data collected for the interview and the authenticity of the data obtained from the interviews are in question.

The selection of participants will be on a voluntary basis, which will make adolescents feel open and free to express their own opinions and provide information about experiences in front of questions and answers. Additionally, data will be used as direct quotes from the interviews without any changes. Again, the superordinate themes prepared by the experts were compared by the evaluators and the Kappa analysis performed to measure the reliability of the agreement was found to be 96%. (Landis & Koach , 1977) This is considered a significant rate for reliability.

In particular, to ensure internal consistency reliability , the Likert scale is used to denote a large number of items based on the mean or average correlation of each item in the measurement instrument, based on its correlation with all other items (Leech , Brett , & Morgan, 2005).

For the sake of external validity, which includes the transferability of the research, the method of collecting, transferring, analyzing and interpreting data was carried out by the researcher in this thesis. In this context, the model of the study, the study group, the data collection tool, the data collection process, the analysis of the data and the interpretation of the theory by generalizing it through comparisons with the studies on the subject in the literature using the analytical generalization method are defined in detail. Before the data collection phase, research ethics were carefully followed at every stage. The researcher first came to St. After receiving permission approval from the ethics committee of Clements University, the Ministry of Education followed the path of obtaining permission from the Ankara Provincial Directorate of National Education through legal and relevant means. Interview questions St. It was submitted to the Clements University Ethics Committee. The researcher started the implementation process of the study after the written approval

of the ethics committee of the Ministry of National Education Ankara Provincial Directorate of National Education in an official letter. Then, the researcher randomly and randomly selected 12th grade students from Vocational High School, Imam Hatip High School and Science High School, which were selected as the sample of the study. The participants were selected as participants and the principals of the relevant selected high schools presented the written permission approval as an official document during the data collection process, and applied the forms of the interview questions and scales in line with the purpose of the study. The informed consent form was explained to the relevant parties in detail and the implementation process continued in line with the permission received. Particular attention was paid to the data collection process, on a voluntary basis and on confidentiality, with the signatures of 17-year-old adolescents. Coding was done to the participants in line with the confidentiality of the study. During the signing of the consent form, participants were clearly informed about their rights not to answer or refuse certain questions for the sake of the sensitivity of the research, and they were assured that they could withdraw from the research if they wished. Particular care was taken to keep all records of this research private and not to share them with other people or institutions.

the internal reliability (consistency) of the research; While transferring the findings, no comments were made and they were directly reported in this thesis .

In order to ensure the external reliability (confirmability) of the research, all data collection tools of the researcher, raw data, super-theme coding that emerged during the analysis process and perceptions that form the subject of the report in line with the data, notes and all documents - data and inferences were presented to an expert in the field for review and confirmation. It was built.

THIRD PART

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The Effect of Demographic Characteristics on Social Anxiety

Their thoughts about whether the social anxiety felt by the senior high school students who participated in the research differ according to their demographic characteristics , what kind of difference there is , and what the factors that create the difference might be were examined.

Participants identified the family's educational status , gender, culture, economic situation, and parent's age as demographic characteristics , and in addition to these , as factors affecting social anxiety ; They stated physical characteristics , exams, genetic and biological factors , family structure, and high school types as effective factors .

Table 3. Effect of Demographic Characteristics on Social Anxiety Table

	Gender	Parental Attitude	Economical situation	Family structure	Physical Properties	Genetic	Parent Educational Status	High School Type	Culture	Parent Age	Exam
K2	√	√		√	√	√	√		√	√	
K3	√	√	√	√			√		√	√	
K1	√			√	√	√	√		√		
K12	√	√	√						√	√	√
K7	√	√			√	√	√		√		
K8	√	√	√				√		√	√	
K9	√	√					√		√	√	
K10	√	√	√	√					√		
K5	√		√					√	√		
K11	√		√						√	√	
K4	√	√		√		√			√		
K6	√		√		√				√		

Looking at Table 4 , while all participants stated the variables "gender" and "culture" as factors affecting social anxiety, seven participants expressed " parental attitude " , six participants expressed "economic status" and " parent's educational status", four participants expressed " family structure " , three participants expressed " physical characteristics " , genetics, It is seen that one participant expressed it as "school/ high school type " and "exam" .

"... So actually we are all the same in terms of stress and anxiety , but I think it reflects us a little more than girls ..." (P1 1 1)

"...Now, in the general way that boys are brought up, they are raised in a more conservative way, and maybe they have less difficulty in speaking in public, not because they have more self-confidence , but because they have more ego . But girls may have more difficulty in general, because they were raised to be more wimpy" (K11 1 2)

"... So, parental attitudes are tighter for them . I don't think this is the case with boys. They can choose any job they want. So, it doesn't affect boys either. But there is pressure on girls . Girls to the parent's situation He chooses accordingly . In other words, the teacher chooses according to the parent, I think most of them ..." (P8 1 2)

".... I believe that the social anxiety of a person from a rich family will be low... It does not matter if it is a boy or a girl, if the family is rich, the anxiety is low, but if it is poor, I think the anxiety will be high ..." (P10 1 3)

"... A divorced family ... Of course, children want their parents to be together no matter what , they want it to be a job , and their divorce creates social anxiety for them too . So no one wants to say "My parents are divorced" around their friends . I see it is quite high here too . As I said, to serious levels of social anxiety, to a non-divorced family according to There is a little more anxiety ..." (P4 1 4)

"...Yes, so if a girl is 17 years old when she wants to enter an environment , she wants to be beautiful, she wants to look good physically , she wants her face to look good . Men definitely have this too , but it is less . More girls have physical features according to anxiety formation..." (P7 1 5)

"...Ultimately it depends on the genetics of the parents . In other words, it may depend on the things he saw or the traumas he experienced when he was a child . There are many factors ..." (P2 1 6)

"... Of course, a child whose parents are highly educated becomes more enterprising and more important when he enters a society . But a child whose mother and father are grocers also has a side of attraction. Here too, the children of families with higher education levels are more enterprising..." (P3 1 7)

"... Girls in families with low educational attainment have high social anxiety . Boys have low social anxiety . I think their social anxiety is low, even in families with low education, children, boys, are much more comfortable..." (P7 1 7)

"... Those who are in a worse school may have a lower superego . More things to lose may decrease . Because going to this business is a result . So, you don't go to good school just to get married" (K5 1 8)

“ Culture is of course a very big factor . Especially for women This is a big factor . In general , there is a constant pressure on women in our society . Of course , men also have it , but not as much as women ...” (P9 1 9)

“I think the age of your parents would have an impact . After all, an elderly parent will have difficulty understanding their child . But the younger ones are more interested . I think they will understand their children better . Older people generally want their children to act in their own way, but younger people are a little more understanding. This situation, of course , reduces stress . It reduces anxiety ... so I think older people have more anxiety and younger people have less anxiety ...” (P12 1 10)

“... I think it increases anxiety in exams . Because people treat you according to the score you get from the exam. If you get a high score, your social life becomes easier, but on the contrary, if you get a low score in the exam, everyone treats you differently ...” (12 1 11)

Among the participants, students attending science high schools stated genetics, gender and physical characteristics as factors of social anxiety , while students of vocational high school and imam hatip high school stated family structure , parental attitude , parental age and parental education as factors of social anxiety .They expressed their situation . The elements of social anxiety expressed by all participants are gender and culture.

Gender, School Type and Parents ' Joint/Separated Status Characteristics on Social Anxiety

The table regarding the views of adolescents on social anxiety in the context of gender, according to the Fully Structured Interview Form of the participants in the research, is given below.

Table 4. Table of the Effects of Gender, School Type and Parental Situation/Separation Characteristics on Social Anxiety

Looking at Table 4, it can be seen that eight female and four male

Code	Gender	Residence	School Type	Parents Separated/Together	I don't allow my rights to be enforced/ I have difficulty defending my rights	I Can/I Cannot Represent the Class Indecisive
K2	Woman	Cankaya	Science High School	Separate	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K3	Woman	Cankaya	Imam Hatip High School	Together	I won't let you lose my rights	Indecisive
K11	Woman	Cankaya	Vocational high School	Together	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K1	Male	Cankaya	Science High School	Together	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K4	Woman	Etimesgut	Science High School	Together	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K6	Woman	Etimesgut	Vocational high School	Separate	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K10	Woman	Etimesgut	Imam Hatip High School	Separate	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K5	Male	Etimesgut	Science High School	Together	Indecisive	Indecisive
K9	Woman	xinjiang	Imam Hatip High School	Separate	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K12	Woman	xinjiang	Vocational high School	Together	Indecisive	Indecisive
K7	Male	xinjiang	Science High School	Separate	I won't let you lose my rights	I can represent the class
K8	Male	xinjiang	Imam Hatip High School	Separate	Indecisive	I can represent the class

participants participated in our research. When we look at the participants, it can be seen that seven students answered the question "I can represent the class" regarding detecting social phobia in their answers to the questions of the fully structured interview form, with "I can represent the class", and three students answered undecided. At the same time, it can be seen that seven students among the participants responded with "I will not allow anyone to violate their rights" regarding self-defense and denial of their rights, and the three students who responded "undecided" were two men and one was a woman. It is seen that four of the participants in our research have separate parents, two participants are male participants whose parents are separated, and four participants are male participants whose parents live together and both

parents live together. It is seen that six out of six participants whose parents are separated answered "I can represent the class", three out of six participants whose parents live together answered "I can represent the class" and three answered "undecided". When looked at by school type ; While one of the five participants from the Science High School said "undecided", four participants said "I can represent the class", one of the three participants from the Vocational High School said "undecided", two participants said "I can represent the class", and one of the four participants from Imam Hatip High School said "I can represent the class". It is seen

Code	Gender	Residence	Family Income Status	I Have/Low Self-Worth
K2	Woman	Cankaya	Upper Middle (50,000-75,000)	I have self worth
K3	Woman	Cankaya	Below Average (15,000-30,000)	I have self worth

that three participants stated as "undecided" and "I can represent the class".

Opinions of Residence and Family Income Characteristics on Self-Worth Consciousness

The table containing the opinions of the participants in the research on self-worth awareness according to their residence address and family income status is given below.

Table 5. Effect of Characteristics of Residence and Family Income Status on Self-Worth Consciousness Table

K11	Woman	Cankaya	Medium (30,000-50,000)	I have self worth
K1	Male	Cankaya	Upper Middle (50,000-75,000)	I have self worth
K4	Woman	Etimesgut	Medium (30,000-50,000)	I have self worth
K6	Woman	Etimesgut	Below Average (15,000-30,000)	I have self worth
K10	Woman	Etimesgut	Medium (30,000-50,000)	I have self worth
K5	Male	Etimesgut	Upper Middle (50,000-75,000)	I have self worth
K9	Woman	xinjiang	Upper Middle (50,000-75,000)	I have self worth
K12	Woman	xinjiang	Below Average (15,000-30,000)	I have low self worth
K7	Male	xinjiang	Medium (30,000-50,000)	I have self worth
K8	Male	xinjiang	Medium (30,000-50,000)	I have self worth

Code	Chinese site	Licence Is he thinking?	Factor affecting undergraduate thought	Undergraduate Degree ?	Social Anxiety
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a fully structured interview and socio-demographic personal information form, four participants from Çankaya District, four from Etimesgut District and four from Sincan District participated in the study. Only one female participant answered the questions "I have low self-worth-I have low self-worth", which were asked to the participants as a resident, with "I have low self-worth". Therefore, three women and one man in Çankaya , three women and one man in Etimesgut, and two men and one woman in Sincan who participated in the study answered "I have self-worth". Considering the family income status of the participants , there are two participants with above middle income, one with below middle income and one with middle income in Çankaya, two participants with middle income, one with above middle income and one with below middle income in Etimesgut, and two participants with middle income and one with middle income in Sincan. The above-middle student responded as "I have self-worth", while the participant from Xinjiang with a below-middle family income responded as "I have low self-worth".

of Gender on Prediction of Educational Progress and Social Anxiety

The table containing the opinions of the participants in the research on the effect of gender on the tendency to study undergraduate / master's degree and its relationship with social anxiety is given below.

K2	Woma n	neuropsychiatry	My interests	neuropsychiatry	I'm a Social Person
K3	Woma n	Nursing	My interests	Yes	I'm a Social Person
K11	Woma n	Indecisive	My interests	I'm undecided	I'm a Social Person
K4	Woma n	Molecular biology and genetics	My interests	Genetic	I'm a Social Person
K6	Woma n	Law	My interests	Judicial Jurisdiction Exam	I'm a Social Person
K10	Woma n	Psychology	My interests	Psychology	I am a very social person
K9	Woma n	Medicine	My interests	Yes	I'm a Social Person
K12	Woma n	Indecisive	I'm undecided	Indecisive	I am at normal level/ I'm bored
K7	Male	economics	I observed around me	No	I'm a Social Person
K8	Male	Indecisive	I'm undecided	No	I am passive
K5	Male	Indecisive	I'm undecided	Indecisive	I'm a Social Person
K1	Male	Mechanical Engineering	My interests	Yes	I'm at Normal Level

Table 6. Table containing their views on the Effect of Gender on Educational Prediction and Social Anxiety

According to the fully structured interview form questions asked to the participants in the research, when the gender tendency to study undergraduate education was examined, a female participant in the research said "Neuropsychology", a female participant said "Nursing", a female participant said "Molecular Biology and Genetics", a female participant said "Law", a female participant said "Law". female participant wanted to study "Psychology", one female participant wanted to study "Medicine ", one female participant wanted to study "undecided", two male participants wanted to study "undecided", one male participant wanted to study "Economics" and the reason for the tendency here is that all eight female participants had their own "area of interest". ", considering the tendency to study for a master's degree, one female participant out of eight said " Neuropsychiatry ", two female participants said "undecided", two female participants said "considering", one female participant said "Genetics", one female participant

said "Psychology". ", one female participant stated that it was "Law" field, two of the four male participants in the research stated that they were not considering a master's degree, one was "undecided" and the other stated that he was "considering but has not determined a field". Additionally, out of eight female participants, six female participants said they were social. To the question "I am a social person", one female participant answered "I am a very social person", one female participant answered "I am bored", and four male participants responded to the same question as "I am a social person", two male participants responded "I am a passive person", and one male participant responded "I am passive". It is seen that one male participant answered "I am at a normal level".

Opinions of High School Senior Adolescents on Self-Definition Styles

The Opinions table of the participants who participated in the research regarding their self-definition styles according to the fully structured interview form questions is given below.

Table 7. Table of Opinions of Adolescents on Self-Definition Styles

How would you describe yourself?	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	K9	K10	K11	K12
I am a social person.		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		√	
I am a very social person.			√							√		
A-I am a social person.												
I am at normal level.	√	√							√			√
I'm bored		√								√		√
I'm so shy												
I am excited.						√		√	√			
I am very excited				√								√
I am active		√	√	√					√			
I'm Very Active					√	√						
I am passive								√				
I am very passive.												
I won't let you lose my rights.	√	√	√	√		√	√		√	√	√	
I have difficulty defending my rights.								√				
I can represent myself	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√				√
I am incapable of representing myself.												
I can represent the class.	√	√		√		√	√		√	√	√	
I cannot represent the class.								√				
If I know when a question is asked in class, I immediately			√			√		√	√			

raise my hand to answer.												
If I know a question is asked in class, I can immediately raise my hand to answer and explain the topic on the board.		√				√						
Even if I know when a question is asked in class, I prefer not to answer if the teacher does not allow it.	√		√	√	√		√			√	√	√
Even if I know when a question is asked in class, if the teacher removes it, I cannot explain the topic on the board.										√		
Even though I know when a question is asked in class, if the teacher removes it, I get very panicked and excited while explaining the topic on the board.												√
I have self-worth.	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
I have low self worth			√									√
My self worth is very low												

Ten of the participants who participated in the research said "I have self-worth", nine said "I am a social person", "I do not allow myself to be denied", "I can represent myself ", two said: "I am a very social person", "I am very excited", "I am very active", "I am very active", "I am a question in class". If I know when asked, I can immediately raise my hand to answer and explain the topic on the board. ", "I have low self-esteem", four of them: "I am at a normal level.", "I am active ", "If I know when a question is asked in class, I immediately raise my hand to answer." three of them are "I'm shy", "I'm excited", one is "I'm passive", " I have difficulty defending my rights", "I cannot represent the class ", "Even if I know when a question is asked in class, I cannot explain the topic on the board if the teacher removes it.", "Even if I know when a question is asked in class, If the teacher removes it, I will panic and get excited while explaining the subject on the board. "eight", "I can represent the class", "Even if I know when a question is asked in class, I prefer not to answer if the teacher does not allow it." The answers to which they responded in the form of "A-I am a social person.", "I am very shy," "I am very passive," and "I am inadequate in representing myself." were included in the fully structured interview form. It was observed that none of the participants answered the questions "I have very low self-worth" and "I have very low self-esteem" .

Opinions of 17-Year-Old Adolescents on Women's Working Situations in Social Life

The table of Opinions of the participants in the research regarding women's work in social life, according to the fully structured interview form questions, is given below.

Table 8. Table of Opinions of Adolescents on the situation of women

Code	Gender	Residence	School Type	Women Should Work	Women Should Not Work
K2	Woman	Cankaya	Science High School	should work	-
K3	Woman	Cankaya	Imam Hatip High School	should work	-
K11	Woman	Cankaya	Vocational high School	should work	-
K1	Male	Cankaya	Science High School	should work	-
K4	Woman	Etimesgut	Science High School	should work	-
K6	Woman	Etimesgut	Vocational high School	should work	-
K10	Woman	Etimesgut	Imam Hatip High School	should work	-
K5	Male	Etimesgut	Science High School	should work	-
K9	Woman	xinjiang	Imam Hatip High School	should work	-

should/shouldn't they work in social life

K12	Woman	xinjiang	Vocational high School	should work	-
K7	Male	xinjiang	Science High School	should work	-
K8	Male	xinjiang	Imam Hatip High School	should work	-

Looking at Table 8, when the answers given by 17-year-old adolescents to the question "should/should not work" regarding women's working life are examined, it is seen that all participants, eight female participants and four male participants, answered "should work".

Opinions of Adolescents on Women's Working/Not Working in Social Life

According to the questions of the fully structured interview form, the questions of the 17-year-old participants in the research were "If women should/shouldn't work, why should they/shouldn't they work?" in their social life. Table 9 showing their answers to the question is given below.

Table 9 . Adolescents' questions such as "Women should/should not work in social life, why?" Opinions Table About

Should Women Work? From where?	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	K9	K10	K11	K12
It may work for interest and personal preference.	√	√	√				√	√			√	√
His/her family should not work because their parents do not want them to			√									
He should not work because his wife prevents him from working.			√									
She can be at home and work to take care of her children.		√	√				√					
Being at home and working due to household chores		√					√					
She can work in accordance with social ethical rules (women should take care of the housework and children at home, men should bring money to the house).		√										
It should work.						√			√			

When we look at the answers given by high school senior adolescents to the question "If women should/should not work in social life, why?", seven of the twelve participants in the study said that they should work at home, saying "She can work for interest and personal preference.", three of them said "She can be at home and work to take care of her children." Two of them expressed the necessity of working at home by saying "He can be at home and work due to housework", two participants said "He should work", and one each said "He should not work because his parents do not want him to", "He should not work because his wife prevents him from working", "Social ethics". It is seen that they responded as follows: "She can work according to the rules (women should take care of the housework and children at home, men should bring money to the house).

Opinions of Adolescents on the reasons why women work in social life

According to the questions of the fully structured interview form, the participants in the research asked women in social life "If they should work, why should they work?" Table 11 showing their answers to the question is given below.

Table 10 . Adolescents' questions such as "If women should work in social life, why should they work?" Table of Opinions on “

“If women should work, why should they work?”	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	K9	K10	K11	K12
Interest should work for personal preference.		√	√		√	√	√		√		√	√
He/she must work to support the family (for economic needs).		√	√									
It should work in accordance with the social state principle (principle of equality)	√	√		√		√		√			√	√
Self-respect- must work for self-worth		√			√	√	√		√		√	√
He must work because his family wants him to.											√	
Must work for												

When Table 10 is examined, eight of the 17-year-old participants who participated in the research said, "He should work for interest and personal

preference.", seven said, "He should work in accordance with the social state principle (principle of equality)," "He should work for self-esteem-self-worth," and two said, "To support the family (economic It is seen that women stated their reasons for participating in working life as "They should work for the requirements" and one of them said "They should work because their family wants them to".

Adolescents: If women should work in social life; In which professions?

Opinions on Should it work?

According to the questions of the fully structured interview form, the participants in the research asked "If women should work, in which areas should they work?" in social life. Table 11 showing their answers to the question is given below.

Table 11 . Adolescents' questions such as "If women should work in social life, in which professions should they work?" Table of Opinions on “

“In which professions should women work?”	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	K9	K10	K11	K12
Can work at a desk	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	
Can work as a teacher	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Can work as a doctor	√	√	√	√		√	√	√		√	√	
Train, Crane etc.Can work as an operator		√		√		√	√			√	√	√
Can work as an artist (singer, painter, musician, actor, etc.)	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	
Politician, Politician can work	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Can work as an imam or teacher		√	√	√		√		√	√	√	√	
Can work as an academic	√	√	√	√		√	√	√		√	√	
Can work as a tailor, greengrocer, tradesman, dishwasher etc.	√	√		√			√	√	√	√	√	
Can work as a journalist	√	√	√	√		√	√	√		√	√	
Can work as a Bus-Minibus Driver	√	√	√	√			√	√		√	√	
Can work as a truck driver	√	√		√			√	√		√	√	√
He can work as the owner of a hotel, workplace, newspaper, teaching institution, market, cafe.	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√	√	√	
Can work as an accountant	√	√		√		√	√	√	√	√	√	
Can work as CIO (senior manager in companies)	√	√	√			√	√	√		√	√	

Can work as an electrician or real estate agent	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Can work as an engineer (Electrical engineer, Civil engineer, etc.)		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
He can work as a Minister, Speaker of the Parliament, Minister of Internal Affairs, Minister of Education.	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Can work as Prime Minister		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Can work as president		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Athlete, Athlete, Swimmer, Licensed can work in sports branches	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
artificial intelligence engineering, Robotics Engineering, Drone Pilot etc.	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
a Pilot, Ship Captain, Soldier , General, General, etc.		√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
He can work in any field he wants.				√		√		√	

Looking at Table 11, adolescents asked, "If women should work in social life, in which professions should they work?" In the examination of their views on “

Eleven participants: “He can work as a teacher”, Ten participants : “He can work at a desk”, “He can work as an artist (Singer, Painter, Musician, Theater actor, etc.)”, “Owner of a hotel, workplace, newspaper, teaching institution, market, cafe "He can work as an Athlete, Athlete, Swimmer, Licensed Sportsman", "He can work as an Artificial Intelligence Engineering, Robotics Engineering, Drone Pilot etc.", "He can work as an Artificial Intelligence Engineering, Robotics Engineering, Drone Pilot etc.. ", Nine participants: "He can work as a doctor", "He can work as an academician", "He can work as a journalist", "He can work as an accountant", "He can work as an engineer (Electrical engineer, Civil engineer etc.)", Eight participants: " "He can work as an imam, a teacher", "He can work as a tailor, greengrocer, tradesman, dishwasher etc. ", "He can work as a bus-minibus driver", "He can work as a truck-truck driver", "He can work as a CIO (senior manager in companies)" , “He can work as CIO (senior manager in companies)”, Seven participants: “Train, Crane etc. "He can work as an operator. " Three participants said: "He can work in any field he wants." It was observed that they made markings such as:

When the professional groups regarding the political representation of women, which is the main theme of our research, are examined; Participants:

To the question "He can work as a Minister, Speaker of the Parliament, Minister of Internal Affairs, Minister of Education"; Among the eight female participants who participated in the research, one female participant left it blank and seven female participants marked it as "able to work". One of the four male participants marked "He can work in any field he wants" and three male participants marked "He can work". A total of ten participants marked "workable".

To the question "Can he work as Prime Minister?" While one of the four male participants said "he can work in any field he wants", one left it blank, a total of two male participants said "he can work", one of the eight female participants left it blank, five female participants answered "he can work", and nine participants out of the total said "he can work". responded.

To the question "Can he work as President?" One of the four male participants said "he can work in any field he wants", one left it blank, a total of two male participants said "he can work", while out of eight female participants, two left it blank, six female participants answered "he can work", and nine participants out of the total responded "he can work". responded.

3.2.Social Relationships and Performance on Social Anxiety

According to the semi-structured interview form questions, the data obtained when examining the effects of the participants participating in the research on women's social relations and performances in social life and on social anxiety are given below in Table 12.

Table 12.Table of the Effect of Social Relationships and Performance on Social Anxiety

	Peer Bullying	Family structure	Parents' Age	Gender	Religionial Belief	Career choice	Parental Attitude	Appearance	Educational Status	Economical situation	Genetic	Culture
K1		√	√	√	√	√	√		√	√	√	√
K2		√	√	√		√	√		√	√	√	
K3		√	√	√		√	√	√	√			
K8		√	√	√			√		√	√		√
K9		√	√	√		√	√		√			
K6			√	√		√		√				√
K12		√		√			√	√				√
K4			√		√		√					√
K7		√							√	√	√	
K10	√		√			√			√			√
K5		√				√			√			
K11				√			√					√

senior high school students participating in the research on the effect of social relations and performance on social anxiety were examined. While the participants generally stated that the factors were gender, religion, culture and family structure, some participants stated that peer bullying, career choice, age status of the parents, and economic status also affected social relations and performance due to social anxiety.

"...Why... I don't know, my peers are generally more critical and critical. Also , since we are older , it is easier to bully and so on. It is easier to talk to adults..." (P10 2 1)

"... If there is a peaceful environment at home, social anxiety will be less. But sometimes it happens like this , for example, they are married but they are not on good terms, there is conflict. Then, their separation is better in terms of anxiety. That means they have more anxiety . This causes people to become more withdrawn and quieter ..." (P1 2 2)

"...The child of a young family will probably have a closer, more intimate relationship with his father , and a young father will be more appealing to a young child.I think there is less anxiety for that child . Since he sees his father as a friend, he can also gain some power. In this way, he can communicate more easily with his environment..." (P2 2 3)

"... Here in society , obviously women , especially girls, are given a lot of respect.I don't think it is. I think men have less anxiety in general ..." (P3 2 4)

"...It is not a thing for women, for example a woman in Iran, to go and enter politics . Because women cannot work there due to religion , even this creates a

concern . I think it is similar in our country . The way of education , the way the country is governed , its beliefs, its social structure and its point of view all cause concern . In my opinion, left and right things are more important than gender for our society . That 's why right wing womanthe candidate wins against the leftist guy ... ” (P4 2 5)

“...Now, if we look at our country when it comes to choosing a profession, there are not many successful female politicians doing anything in our country yet. So, there is Meral Akşener , but it cannot be said that she is very successful either . What I mean to say is that in Turkey and around the world , men are more prominent in politics and things like politics . And men seem to be more successful ...” (P5 2 6)

“... Therefore, the family's behavior also affects anxiety, and I think families can put more pressure on their daughters . Therefore, even if the girls do not want it, their families can choose whatever they want...” (P9 2 7)

“... Now, as I go to their office, is my clothes neat or not? Is it beautiful? It actually does something . It creates anxiety ... ” (P6 2 8)

“... Of course, from the girl's perspective, if a girl's father is rich, an academician is more important in relationships. I think it shows more variability in those girls. If a girl's father is an academic or rich, she will be more self-confident. But for someone who is a grocer's daughter, something else happens. It may rarely happen that a rich man has a bad education ... ” (P8 2 9 10)

“... Women feel anxiety more than men . So boys, of course, girlsaccording to a little more emotionless . Women also secrete hormones, whether they are estrogen or something else . Forests are biological , yes. Biologically, women tend to be emotional ...” (P7 2 11)

“... Habits from the past because of what they appear to be . I think it generally differs more from girls . There is more pressure ... ” (P12 2 12)

Senior high school students who participated in the research , as concerns affecting social life ; They stated that peer bullying includes gender, family structure , age of parents , culture , education and economic status, genetic structure and appearance . Among the participants, students attending science high schools generally stated that, along with genetic factors , as factors affecting social life and performance , the educational status of the parents has an effect on the child and also affects the economic situation . Students attending vocational studies generally stated that gender , family structure and the age of the parents have an effect on the child . Students who go to Imam Hatip High School are social They stated that religious factors , culture and family structure affect life the most .

3.3. Adolescents' Views on Women's Political Representation

who participated in the research regarding the political representations of women in Turkey were examined . As a result of the review, the following table was created in 14.

Table 13. Table of Adolescents' Opinions on the Political Representation of Women

	Regional Differences	Gender	Parental Attitude	Education	Income status	School Type	Age
K1	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
K2	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
K3	√	√	√	√	√		√
K9	√	√	√			√	√
K12	√	√		√		√	√
K4	√	√	√			√	
K5	√		√	√			√
K6		√		√	√	√	
K7	√		√	√			√
K10		√	√	√	√		
K11	√	√			√	√	
K8		√		√	√		

Adolescents stated that women's representation in the political arena is low in Turkey, and the factors affecting this are the attitudes of parents and the attitude of society, perspectives on gender, income and education level, regional differences, age and school types.

“...There is some pressure on women in our society . While there is a lot of pressure in the east, this pressure is a little less in the west . When there is more pressure, there is less representation ...” (P1 3 1)

“... In Turkey, they may be subjected to more pressure at work due to sexism. They may be despised just because they are women . This may have brought them a lack of self-confidence . When you lack self-confidence, it becomes difficult to represent ...” (P4 3 2)

“...Our society has greater equality between women and men .is ignored. Therefore, politicalThe same thing happens in the field ...” (P2 3 3)

“... Education is important in politics, of course . Some of the current MPs have already received training in their own fields ...” (P10 3 4)

“... high income It would be better in politics . I think this is the case in Turkey . It doesn't matter whether you are male or female , if you are rich and right-wing, you will advance quickly in politics ...” (P8 3 5)

“... Because the schools are usually chosen by the parents ... so even if you don't want it, sometimes it can be a profession you like later on . For example, I have a friend around me. He is very interested in politics . I don't know if it might happen in the future, after all , we are an imam hatip school and we are girls...” (P9 3 6)

“...So I think this is due to our society . People listen more easily when they see an old person , but the same does not happen when they are young ... I think the same goes for politics ...” (P12 3 7)

Concerning the political representation of women in Turkey, adolescents have expressed their opinions that there are differences from region to region, that education regarding representation is important , that women do not have much representation space because they are exposed to pressure from society, and that the older the mandate representatives are, the more they are taken into consideration by the nation. Students attending science high schools stated that there is a difference between men and women in political representation and that the reason for this is the attitudes of their parents. Vocational and Imam Hatip High School students stated that there is generally pressure from the family in their career choices, that is why there are very few young women considering politics , and that income is a big factor in politics .

3.4.Relationship Table Between Women's Political Representation and Social Phobia

The thoughts of senior high school students participating in the research regarding the relationships between women's political representations and social phobia were examined . The data is presented in Table 14 below.

Table 14. Relationship Table between Women's Political Representation and Social Phobia

	Social Pressure	Family Attitude	Regional Differences	Age	Educational Status	Gender	Culture	Genetic Elements	Economical situation
K1	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	✓
K2	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
K3	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		
K4	✓	✓	✓		✓			✓	✓
K5	✓	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓	
K6	✓	✓		✓		✓	✓		✓

K7	√	√			√		√	√	√
K8	√	√	√				√		√
K11		√	√		√		√		√
K9	√			√		√	√		
K10	√			√		√	√		
K12		√			√	√	√		

As factors affecting political representation and social phobia, adolescents identified ten participants as "social pressure", family attitude, six participants as "regional differences", four participants as "age", eight participants as "education", six participants as "gender", eleven participants as "culture". , four participants expressed it as "genetic factors" and seven participants expressed it as "economic situation" .

"...According to our society's point of view, women just sit at home, take care of the children, do the housework, etc. The field of education is the same, as is the field of education. The pressure on women is against greater representation. But men are more comfortable about this. They can easily enter politics and business life..." (P2 4 1)

"... Children are manipulated a lot by their parents. The child does not like the profession at first, but over time he may like it... But parents put pressure and manipulate their children because of their expectations from their own experiences..." (P5 4 2)

"...I think this situation varies from region to region. For example, because there is more pressure on women in the East, they have more social phobia. There, parents generally decide girls' school and career choices. But when we get west, there's less going on. Since there is not much pressure in the West, girls can talk easily and choose the school and profession they want..." (P9 4 3)

"...In our society, older people always get better rest. Even if young people try to talk, they are afraid to talk. But adults are not like that..." (P12 4 4)

"...Education, our MPs have received training in their own fields. However, there may be more male MPs. Because parents usually decide where girls go to school, girls cannot choose this field very often..." (P4 4 5)

"...There seems to be a little more pressure on girls than on boys. So I think so..." (P10 4 6)

"...Adults raise their children with what they have learned before. Before, girls stayed at home and took care of the housework. Boys were more comfortable. He could choose whatever he wanted and choose the profession he wanted. Yes, the situation is not as bad as before, but I think there is still a little bit of this situation..." (P11 4 7)

“...I think it's a genetic thing. In other words, women feel more pressure because they are genetically emotional. I think they are very happy with their representation situation. I think...men can work calmer because they are not emotional. They are more successful in politics because they act logically without pressure...” (P7 4 8)

“...To be successful in politics you need money. He who has money rises by any means necessary. Oh, and of course you'll be right-wing. I don't think gender makes any difference in this case. If you want to be successful in Turkey, you must be a right-winger and have a good source of money...” (P8 4 9)

Participants stated social pressure, family attitude, regional differences, age, education, gender, genetic factors and economic status as factors affecting the relationship between women's political representation and social phobia. In addition, while students attending science high schools stated genetic factors, education, culture and family attitudes as factors affecting women's political representation and social phobia, students attending vocational high schools stated social pressure, gender factor, age and social pressure. Students attending religious high schools stated social pressure and regional differences as factors affecting women's political representation and social phobia.

3.5.His Attitudes Towards Women's Political Representations and His Views Towards Women's Political Representations in the Context of Gender Perception

The attitudes of the male and female senior high school students who participated in the research towards women's political representations and their thoughts about whether women's political inclinations do not significantly predict their intentions in the context of gender perception were examined. As a result of the examination, the participants expressed their opinion that it had a positive or negative effect .

Table 15. Table of Women's Political Representations in the Context of Women's Attitudes Towards Political Representations and Gender Perception

	Positive Impact	Negative effect
K1	√	
K2	√	
K3		√
K4	√	
K5		√
K6		√
K7	√	

K8		√
K9		√
K10	√	
K11		√
K12		√

ten participants stated that it had a positive effect on Women's Political Representations in the Context of Women's Attitudes Towards Political Representations and Gender Perception , while seven stated that it had a negative effect.

"...over time, women also started to raise their voices. Considering previous times, the pressure on women seems to have decreased a little now. This will decrease even more in the future. They will consider going into politics. They will be more comfortable in their career choices..." (P1 5 1)

"...I don't think it's like the old times. With education, people began to become more aware of some things. Parents started trying to understand their children. I think the number of women will increase in the future. I think women will be represented in every field..." (P2 5 1)

"...I think even the fact that women make their voices heard shows that the pressure is decreasing. This will get even better in the future. I think women will have easier choices in the future..." (P4 5 1)

"...I think it's a matter of self-confidence. In other words, if a man or woman has self-confidence, they will of course be successful in politics. However, I do not know when the pressure on women will be lifted. Because of the pressure and lack of self-confidence, women are not heard much in politics. When men have high self-confidence, they are more successful..." (P6 5 2)

"...I think women will be represented in every field in the future. Society's perspective has begun to change, at least in the west. Although it is still the same in the east, women have started to make their voices heard, which I think will make their representation situation better..." (P7 5 1)

"...I think why shouldn't women be represented in politics ? I mean , it's not like they always have to deal with housework and children. I think they will have more voices in business life and politics in the future..." (P10 5 1)

"...When we think about our society, I think there has always been pressure on women. I think women cannot be very successful in politics due to marriage, children etc...." (P3 5 2)

"...Women are emotional by their biological nature. There will always be pressure because they act emotionally. If their self-confidence is high, they can be more successful in politics..." (P5 5 2)

"...Women always have more responsibilities. He is under pressure from the society, his parents choose the school, and he tries to love the school and profession that his parents forced him to send him to before he can have the profession he wants. I don't think this will change much..." (P8 5 2)

"...I think women's political representation does not have a big impact. So women generally take care of the housework and children. Everyone expects these from him..." (P9 5 2)

"... I think women are happy with their current situation. So they can make their voices. This means that the pressure has decreased. So I don't think there will be a big change..." (P11 5 2)

"...I think women think they should take care of the housework and children. I think this needs to change. Women need to be in more different professions. For example, why shouldn't there be a female poet..." (P12 5 2)

Among the participants, senior students attending science high schools, stated that gender roles will change with the political representation of women, that they will be in a better situation with the change in education and parental attitudes, and that the representation of women will increase not only in politics but also in other areas. Vocational high school and religious high school senior students expressed their thoughts that women's gender roles will continue in the future and therefore their political representation will not show a positive development.

Opinions of High School Senior Students on Women's Political Representation

High school senior students were asked the question "What are your thoughts about women's political representation in Turkey?" in the fully structured Interview Form. Why? (Deputy, President, Prime Minister, President etc.), in the political profession; is successful. / is unsuccessful." Their opinions were taken by asking questions. The data is given in Table 16 below.

Table16. "Women are successful/unsuccessful in politics. Table of Opinions on the question "If it is not successful, why is it unsuccessful?"

"Women are successful/unsuccessful in politics. If it is not successful, why is it unsuccessful?"	K1	K2	K3	K4	K5	K6	K7	K8	K9	K10	K11	K12

They are not successful because of social judgments	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
They are not successful due to household responsibilities (housework, etc.).		√	√	√	√	√	√		
They are not successful due to child responsibility.	√	√	√	√	√	√	√		
They are not successful because they did not receive education.		√		√	√				
They are not successful due to lack of self-confidence / self-worth.		√		√					
They are not successful due to social phobia (inability to express in public, inability to speak, excitement, etc.).()	√	√	√	√					
They are not successful because their family, spouse-mother-father-sibling-brother do not support or oppose them.		√		√	√				
They are not successful because it is a profession that does not have sufficient recognition in Turkey.		√		√					
They are not successful because there is no equality between men and women.	√	√	√	√	√				
Politics is a suitable profession for men.							√		
They are successful		√		√				√	

When the table above is examined, Nine participants; "They are not successful because of social judgments", Seven participants; "They are not successful because of the responsibility of children ", Five participants; "They are not successful due to household responsibilities (housework, etc.)", "They are not successful because there is no equality between men and women", Four participants ; "They are not successful due to social phobia (inability to express in public, inability to speak, excitement, etc.) ." Fly _participant ; "They are not successful because they did not receive education ", "They are not successful because their family, spouse-

mother-father-sibling-brother does not support or oppose them. ”Two participant; “ They are not successful because of their lack of self-confidence / self-worth.”, “They are not successful because it is a profession that does not have sufficient recognition in Turkey.”, One participant; “Politics is a suitable profession for men”, All three participants said; They responded, “They are successful.”

3.6.L is the Table of Metaphors of Senior Students towards the Concept of "Political Representation of Women" in the Context of Gender

The metaphors of the senior high school students participating in the research regarding the political representations of women are given in the table below.

Table 17. Metaphors of Senior High School Students towards the Concept of "Political Representation of Women" in the Context of Gender

	Iron fist	Compass	Queen bee	Breaking free from your chains	Bird	scam	Intelligence	Ice	Confidence	Light	Crown	Freedom
K1	√											
K2		√										
K3			√									
K4				√								
K5					√							
K6						√						
K7							√					
K8								√				
K9									√			
K10										√		
K11											√	
K12												√

“...I can compare it to Iron Fist . Because really, a woman is a dominant character, even though she is a woman...” (P1 6 1)

“... compass. To the women who will follow like this, that Because it sets an example for those who want to choose a career path and shows what can be done ...” (P2 6 2)

“... Queenbee. Queenbee , okay. Because of his strength ... Despite the difficulties ...” (P3 6 3)

“...I think women should be freed from their chains . They should be free...”(P4 6 4)

“... I can compare it to a bird . I mean, it's like freedom . Like being free ...” (P5 6 5)

“...I think women should stop cheating on themselves . Don't let them fool you. They are used to the old things and the old thoughts , so I think this situation is like a deception ...” (P6 6 6)

“...I think we can call it intelligence . After all, due to the biological structure of women, their brain structures seem to be encoded in the patriarchal structure...” (P7 6 7)

“...ice. Because, as I said, they are very successful when they have the right environments. In other words, they can express themselves without being under pressure...” (P8 6 8)

“...I think we can call it self-confidence . After all, self-confident women are everywhere, always.

They will be successful ...” (P9 6 9)

“... Let's take light as an example then. So, like the light in the dark ...” (P10 6 10)

“...I mean crown, it is the thing we wear on our heads .I think the queen has a crown. I mean, I think women are superior to men whose intelligence will decrease ...” (P11 6 11)

“... I could say freedom, for example . Because women's participation in politicsprejudice needs to be broken ...” (P12 6 12)

Senior high school students who participated in the research compared the political representations of women to the iron fist , crown, freedom, queen bees , ice, freedom, intelligence, compass, light, bird, deception and liberation from chains .

3.7. Gender Perception on Social Phobia

Findings regarding whether gender perception has an impact on social phobia in 17-year-old adolescents and what kind of impact it has are given in the table below.

Table18. Relationship Table Between Gender Perception and Social Phobia

Social Anxiety ↓	Genderperception →	one	2	2	3	4	5
		Perception of Gender	Perception of Gender	Perception of Gender	Perception of Gender	Perception of Gender	Perception of Gender
Social Anxiety 1		-.034	.078	.078	.002	.151*	-.069
Social Anxiety 2		-.072	.054	-.047	.038	-.056	.024
Social Anxiety 3		-.020	-.022	-.053	.005	.023	.000
Social Anxiety 4		.000	.060	.027	.000	.101	.025
Social Anxiety 5		.059	-.073	.074	.051	.089	.081
Social Anxiety 6		.134*	-.009	.040	.058	-.146*	.086
Social Anxiety 7		-.002	-.105	.013	.016	-.057	.074
Social Anxiety 8		-.007	.035	.010	.092	-.070	.015
Social Anxiety 9		.055	-.117	-.007	.069	-.118	.072
Social Anxiety 10		.015	-.084	-.030	.088	-.024	.093
Social Anxiety 11		-.020	-.180**	.061	.066	-.120	.046
Social Anxiety 12		.010	.005	-.055	-.060	-.080	.022
Social Anxiety 13		-.008	-.051	-.019	.010	.051	-.061
Social Anxiety 14		-.018	.076	-.030	.102	-.137*	.065
Social Anxiety 15		.033	.118	.044	.082	.012	.026
Social Anxiety 16		-.014	.028	-.012	.079	-.112	.170
Social Anxiety17		-.092	.025	-.066	.039	-.001	.080
Social Anxiety 18		.023	.018	.023	.019	-.060	.023
Social Anxiety 19		-.062	-.055	-.054	.004	-.007	.028
Social Anxiety 20		.062	-.029	.035	.093	-.066	.102
Social Anxiety 21		.044	.028	-.012	.079	-.112	.170**
Social Anxiety 22		.107	.005	.000	-.027	-.029	.048
Social Anxiety 23		.190**	.027	.069	.113	-.059	-.203**
Social Anxiety 24		.016	.010	-.098	-.031	.006	.095
Social Anxiety 25		-.002	.043	-.084	.077	-.021	.119
Social Anxiety26		.050	-.014	.007	.084	-.031	.097
Social Anxiety27		.038	.037	.019	.074	-.101	-.042
Social Anxiety28		-.042	.011	-.001	-.061	.015	-.040
Social Anxiety 29		.065	-.004	.046	.114	-.161**	.136*
Social Anxiety 30		-.013	-.053	.034	-.023	-.067	-.021
Social Anxiety 31		.026	.040	-.025	.050	-.070	.027
Social Anxiety 32		.041	.017	.078	-.007	-.054	.084
Social Anxiety 33		.060	.016	.068	.125*	-.120	.131*
Social Anxiety 34		.066	-.019	.039	.112	-.146*	.131*
Social Anxiety35		-.001	.025	-.039	-.008	-.114	.014
Social Anxiety 36		.078	.041	.001	.077	.009	.019
Social Anxiety37		.072	.034	.008	-.029	-.073	-.003
Social Anxiety38		.127*	-.006	.090	.010	-.026	.051
Social Anxiety 39		.004	-.104	.046	.071	-.092	.138*
Social Anxiety 40		-.056	-.065	.098	-.060	-.017	.165**

* Correlation is significant at the 0.01

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05

When we look at the table , there is a positive relationship between social anxiety 1 and gender perception 4, a positive relationship between social anxiety 6 and gender perception 1, a negative relationship between social anxiety 6 and gender perception 4, and a negative relationship between social anxiety 11 and gender perception 2. There appears to be a relationship. There is a negative relationship between social anxiety 14 and gender perception 5, a positive relationship between social anxiety 16 and gender perception 6, a highly positive relationship between social anxiety 23 and gender perception 1, a high level of social anxiety 23 and gender perception 5. There is a high level of negative relationship between social anxiety 29 and gender perception 4 . There is a positive relationship between social anxiety 29 and gender perception 5, there is a positive relationship between social anxiety 33 and gender perception 3, there is a positive relationship between social anxiety 33 and gender perception 3, there is a positive relationship between social anxiety 33 and gender perception 5. It is seen that there is a negative relationship between social anxiety 34 and gender perception 4, and a positive relationship between social anxiety 34 and gender perception 5. It is seen that there is a positive relationship between social anxiety 38 and gender perception 1, a positive relationship between social anxiety 39 and gender perception 5, and a high level positive relationship between social anxiety 40 and gender perception 5. However, according to the table, it is found that there is a positive relationship between social perception and gender perception.

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION

It is thought that determining the attitudes of 17-year-old adolescents in terms of school types (Imam Hatip, Vocational and Science High School) in the context of their level of awareness towards the political representation of women in the context of gender before the voting age is important for the political representation of women in the country, and again in the context of women and girls in the context of gender in Turkey. It is thought that determining the attitudes of

adolescents towards male political roles is important and, in line with the emerging indicators, observing and evaluating the attitudes of the adolescent population considered to be before the voting age in our country is important in the context of the upcoming political process and, accordingly, the country's management policies. It can be said that the lack of sufficient literature on the subject of this research increases the importance of the study.

In cases where Social Phobia is effective in adolescents, situations such as interest in lessons, active participation in the lesson, having the right to speak independently, being able to carry out the responsibilities freely, and self-esteem are very important factors. In the evaluation made in terms of school type, it was observed that students attending science high schools had higher social anxiety than students attending vocational high schools or imam hatip high schools, but they were more future-oriented than students of vocational high schools and imam hatip high schools. While it is observed that vocational high school students and imam hatip high school students are more focused on a professional career, self-worth is the ability to choose their own independent wishes, to realize their decisions, they tend to use their own personal preferences rather than the needs and expectations of the society they live in, and they tend to make independent decisions and pursue a career accordingly. It was observed that they were targeted, and that they were in the same line with the science high school students in terms of the place of women both in working life and in the political arena. 17-year-old adolescents are not under the gender perception of women, they are independent, they prioritize their own vision and desires, they tend to work towards their own interests and implement their career plans despite variables such as family, relatives or society, and although there is an invisible gender perception, male and female students have a common gender perception. His judgment is "I do the profession I want, not what they (family, relatives, society demands and expectations) want, because my interest is in this direction. It was observed that the answers were expressed as ". The impressions of 17-year-old adolescents about the political arena are that girls have little political interest, that the society and family are factors in this, and that they think women should take part in the political arena. However, they put forward the male-dominated structure (perception) and the patriarchal view as the reason for women's

decision to take less part in politics. It was observed that the structure stated that even if women showed sufficient activity in the field and were successful , they could not gain a place. In terms of school type, all 12th grade students, regardless of their family income (low/high/medium), married/ divorced status, number of siblings, and the region they stay (Çankaya, Etimesgut, Sincan), all have self-worth and are independent (family, relative, It was observed that they were able to make decisions on almost every issue (despite society's expectations), and that they were still determined to realize their own wishes, even though they were influenced by family judgments and judgments. Again, it was observed that adolescents think that it is normal for women to do all of the professions arising from gender-based stereotypes determined by social judgments, without discrimination against professions such as crane operator , prime minister, president, tailor, imam. It was observed that male and female students of Imam Hatip High School, especially women, had overcome occupational stereotypes and stated that they could even choose to be a crane operator freely and independently, and especially at their own will. Just as a different evaluation, an interview emerged that emphasized the priority of sexist attitudes, especially that women can do housework and raise children at home because the anatomical structure of a male student in science high school is dominant. In addition, almost all adolescents aged 17 years of age are self-esteemed, independent, and do not have the anxiety of social phobia in a social environment. One student, who does not have social phobia anxiety, cannot answer the question without asking the teacher while the other 11 students say that they can raise their hand even if the teacher does not give them the right to speak, if they know the question asked, and they do not show any anxiety while explaining the topic. He represents what he has not experienced, both himself and his class. It was observed that they stated that they would not experience any fear or anxiety. It has been observed that the academic success levels of students who do not experience social anxiety are also high, and especially in terms of professional careers, most of the vocational high school and imam hatip high school students prefer career-oriented jobs after high school, and they choose these choices based on their own interests rather than the influence of family or social environment. An important detail that stands out from the study is that although most of the science high school students have determined their future career choices, 3 students could not determine them

fully and stated that they would determine them in line with their examinations of a few areas. It was observed that the students were in their final year regarding their career choices and that the underlying reason why they had question marks about a university or career was that they were either undecided or did not want to experience difficulties due to the economic factors in the country, so they stated that they would decide on a choice point after passing the exam.

In general, it is shaped by the society because the people who make up the society grow up according to the society in which they grow up, that is, the cultural-social-economic structure in the society. Due to the gender stereotypes resulting from this situation, it is seen that the position of women in political life is generally ignored and does not coincide with the concept of gender equality, which cannot go beyond a legal concept that should be, and has a more masculine structure. While all countries in the world are experiencing this situation, the gap in gender equality between men and women in the political arena is quite high in developing countries. Our country is among the developing countries and the gender equality threshold is quite high. The main factor here is the society in which one grows up and the concepts of gender judgment patterns and gender socialization that have been transferred from past to present within the society . In accordance with these concepts, the individual who grows up in the family, the smallest structural unit that makes up the society, eats, drinks, moves, thinks, acquires a profession and is even buried after his death, according to the expectations of the society in line with the main variable of gender. Therefore, society positions the individual's entire life, from the moment of birth to the post-mortem phases . In this respect, gender judgment is a very important invisible perception. Politically , due to this situation, we can count the gender factor as the main factor in the male structuring in societies in general, including the use of political tools in political processes (decision making, taking active part, holding rallies, influencing the environment, etc.) . Voting, which is a means of political decision-making in our country, is equal and compulsory for all men and women over the age of 18 . Considering that senior high school students will take an active role in political decision-making processes after the end of high school, according to this research, senior high school adolescents are not oppressed under the social stereotypes imposed from the past, women should stay at home,

women should not work, women should not work, women should not be oppressed by social stereotypes imposed from the past, and women should not work. They show an attitude against many gender roles , such as their orientation towards professions that will not force them and that they can come home after work and do the housework, and that adolescents are no longer independent from society, free, and are not drowned in any stereotypes, they themselves have a more vision and perception of life in line with their more global observations. It was observed that they both had a professional career perception. It was observed that male adolescents and female adolescents have high self-esteem, have high self-esteem, and are able to choose a life and professional career with self-consciousness, in contrast to situations such as being worthless, passive, not finding it right to work and doing housework and raising children, which are also a result of gender judgment patterns.

The traditions, beliefs and value judgments of the society in which people grow up since childhood become a kind of taboo, and the society has an expectation from the individual as a result of his/her cultural reflection in line with the gender variable. This reveals the close relationship between gender and culture. Vocational orientation, on the other hand, refers to the process that enables the individual to continue his/her education at the end of his/her entire life, and it refers to the preference stage in career orientation after high school. In this sense, high school is of particular importance as it is considered as the stepping stone for senior individuals to their final profession, which we call university. In this sense, as individuals' career processes are shaped according to the society in which they grow up, the individual can step into university life or working life in the final year of high school by looking at variables such as environment, family, friends and interests. Since gender defines a set of identities and roles for the individual as male and female, at the moment of birth, it is seen that the individual can step into a professional career in this direction as he grows up according to the expectations of the society. Although variables such as the economic impact of the family, education level, number of siblings, whether parents are married or divorced are important factors in career choice, it can be said that the biggest factor is gender stereotypes and gender socialization variables. In this research, it was found that high school senior adolescents overcome these stereotypes in terms of school type (Science-

Vocational-Imam Hatip), gender, and make more individual decisions in line with their own interests. It was observed that they developed the belief that they could make professional choices in line with their interests and gender equality requirements, and that they also adopted the belief that if their interests and desires were to play a role in the political arena, they should also take part in this field. It was observed by all participants that especially social judgments are not a valid perception in today's conditions, and that, unlike in the past, women and men should have free will in their life and professional choices in every field.

It was observed that the serious difference in the masculine structure's perception of family life or in working life and political arena was overcome with this study. However, there are 11 participants who stated that there is still a small social perception that women cannot be in the political field, but that adolescents can overcome this and that if women want to take part in the political field, receiving education starting from high school will contribute to the knowledge of all adolescents. This study shows. While the sexist division of labor, which is the main indicator of the patriarchal system, is a serious obstacle to women having a say in the political arena, it can be stated that this obstacle has been removed with this study. Because the perception of gender, which prevents women from integrating with political power, is defined as a serious problem. It can be said that global perception changes are the main reflection of the change in the structure and perception of the whole society, and this study clearly reflects the formal change in terms of adolescents. 51% of Türkiye's population consists of women. It is seen that while women constitute more than half of the population, the patriarchal structure ignores the male-prioritized woman and this traditional structure still continues. As in almost every field, the highest share of masculine structuring is seen in the political field. It is the responsibility of the masculine gender to represent, spread, establish and grow ideologies. Here, the concept of belief is also variable for our country, and the definition of women's inability to produce policies and their duty to meet the needs of the wife of the house, husband and children dominates both gender stereotypes and belief values. The prevailing opinion is that women cannot be as rationalistic in their perception of thought as men, that they have a more emotional, naive and fragile nature, and therefore men can take more successful, determined and fearless

steps in political decisions. This study has shown that adolescents do not adopt stereotypes and that women do not accept any social or religious beliefs if they are interested. They express their opinion that they can and should successfully take part in the political arena without bowing to their stereotypes . Considering that women are the ones who understand women best, it is thought that women should also have a say in politics. In addition, giving politics courses starting from high school in order to represent self-worth, self-respect, and the rights of themselves and those around them, and that both men and women can contribute positively to gender equality, reflect the egalitarian structure in their lives, become aware of their own selves with the elements of self-worth, self-respect, and again this study It can be stated that social anxiety can be eliminated from the very beginning, with the prediction that individuals will be prevented from having difficulty in expressing themselves in its relationship with social anxiety, which is an important concept in society . It is also thought that the political courses given in high schools will pave the way for women to take an active role in the political field, instead of being dependent on men, rather than being passive, and will have a positive contribution. It can be stated that with the reflection of equality between men and women, which is an indicator of democratic life, women can no longer be an object but a subject. Instead of the traditional concept of good mother, good wife, women are now structured as successful women and successful women politicians, and it is thought that women are important in political life. 21st century While it is a century in which developments occur one after another, the continuation of the traditionalist structure in every field can be described as a barricade against the development of countries. When sexist stereotypes are prevented from being established in individuals starting from their educational processes, and especially when the finding that social anxiety disorder begins in high school is not ignored, this study shows that adolescents have shown an improvement in overcoming the social structure, judgments and beliefs, and with this political education, they have a healthier life. It can be said that it can happen.

SUGGESTIONS

The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between adolescents' attitudes towards women's political participation in the context of gender and social

anxiety. The first onset of social anxiety occurs in high school. Studies show that gender perception affects the entire lives of individuals, but global developments have caused changes in our country as well, and adolescents' lifestyle and professional career choices are determined in line with their interests. It has been observed that social stereotypes or sexist approaches do not have the same impact as before. Recommendations based on the research results are given below. Since social anxiety emerges especially during adolescence, it is thought that including it in the curriculum so that adolescents can express themselves comfortably and have a say in the political field, which is an important position of the country's administration, and to achieve gender equality in a democratic organization, will make a significant contribution to both adolescents and women and men who will work in the field. It is thought that individuals will be able to gain good communication and self-expression throughout their lives, such as public speaking, self-expression, self-worth and self-respect, thus being productive in communication, which is the most important communication power of individuals with each other. At the same time, it is important to carry out studies to prevent social anxiety disorder, to recognize and treat social anxiety disorder in childhood and adolescence, and it is thought that it would be useful to conduct guidance studies in high schools. It is thought that it would be beneficial to organize more systematically and widely, with the support of the Ministry of National Education, large-scale informative studies about the developmental processes of adolescents, their needs, the processes they experience and/or may experience that may cause anxiety, with the participation of adolescents, teachers and school guidance services. The following suggestions can be made for future research: Relational scanning method was applied in the research. Experimental or observational studies may be conducted in future studies. It is thought that it is important to repeat the research with more participants and support it with different studies regarding the generalizability of the research.

APPENDICES

Annex 1. Parental Consent Form

Dear Parent;

This study, in which your child will participate, is a scientific research application to be carried out between 20.11.2023 and 31.01.2024, under the name "***Examination of the Relationship Between Adolescents' Attitudes towards the Political Representation of Women in Turkey in the Context of Gender and Social Phobia***". Goal of the Research: *The purpose of this research To examine the relationship between 17-year-old adolescents' attitudes towards the political representation of women in Turkey and social phobia (anxiety) in the context of gender.*

Research Application: It is in the form of Survey and Interview / Observation.

The research is carried out with the permission of the Turkish Ministry of National Education and the school administration. Participation in the research application is entirely voluntary. Your child is free to participate in the study or not. The research does not pose any undesirable effects or risks for your child. Your child's participation **is entirely up to your will** , you can refuse or leave at any stage. In case of non-participation or withdrawal from the research, students' academic achievements will not affect their relationships with the school and their teachers.

No identifying information is requested from students in the study. The answers will be kept completely confidential and will be evaluated only by the researchers.

Applications generally do not contain questions or situations that may cause personal discomfort. However, if your child feels uncomfortable with the questions or any other reason during the participation, he/she is free to abandon the answering task and leave. In this case, the necessary assistance will be provided to relieve the discomfort. Your child can withdraw at any time after participating in the study. In such a case , it will be sufficient to tell the person applying the data collection tool that he will not complete the study . Not participating in the survey or giving up after participating will not impose any responsibility on your child.

If you have any questions before approving, do not hesitate to ask. After the study is completed, you can contact us by phone or e-mail to ask questions and request information about the results.

Regards,

Arařtırmacı : Nazmi ESKİ / Öğretmen

İletişim bilgileri : Çankaya ANKARA

*Velisi bulunduğum sınıfı numaralı öğrencisi
.....'in yukarıda açıklanan arařtırmaya katılmasına izin veriyorum.
(Lütfen formu imzaladıktan sonra çocuğunuzla okula geri gönderiniz*).*

.../.../.....

İsim-Soyisim İmza:

Annex2. Socio -demographic Personal Information Form

Veli Adı-Soyadı :
Dear participants,
Tel: 0312 222 2222

This research was conducted by the University of St. It is being conducted within the scope of Clements University Psychology Department Undergraduate Thesis and your answers to the questions will be used only for this research. You do not need to write your name and surname. There is no right or wrong answer to any question.

In order to contribute to scientific research, it is extremely important that you answer the questions sincerely and sincerely and do not leave any questions blank. I kindly ask you to fill in the () sections of the personal information form below and mark (x) where you see any gaps.

Thank you in advance for your contribution to the research.

Personal Information Form

1- Your age: 1) 16 () 2) 17 () 3) 18 ()

2- Your gender: 1) Female () 2) Male ()

3- School and department you are studying:

.....

4- How would you define your socio -economic level?

1)Lower (0 – 15.000 TL) () 2)Below Middle (15.000-30.000) ()

3) Middle (30,000-50,000) () 4)Above Middle 50,000-75,000 () 5)Upper (75,000 - above) ()

5- What is your mother's education level?

1) Primary school () 2) Secondary school () 3) High school () 4) University () 5) Master's degree () 6) Doctorate ()

6- What is your father's educational background?

1) Primary school () 2) Secondary school () 3) High school () 4) University () 5) Master's degree () 6) Doctorate ()

7- What is your mother's employment status?

1) Not working () 2) Working in the public sector () 3) Working in the private sector ()
5)Uninsured () 6)Paid employee () 7)Retired () 8) Tradesman ()
9) Other ()

8- What is your father's employment status?

1) Not working () 2) Working in the public sector () 3) Working in the private sector ()
5)Uninsured () 6)Paid employee () 7)Retired () 8) Tradesman ()
9) Other ()

9- Your mother and father; 1) Lives together () 2) Separated ()

3) My father is in his second marriage and I live with my mother. ()
4) My father is in his second marriage and I live with my father. ()
5) My mother is in her second marriage and I live with my father. ()
6) My mother is in her second marriage and I live with my mother. ()
7) Other

10 – Are you considering a bachelor's degree?

1)Yes ; If so, in which field are you considering a bachelor's degree?
.....
2)If no; From where ? Because;

11- Why do you want the undergraduate field you chose?

1. My area of interest () 2. My mother wants it () 3. My father wants ()
4. I observed it around me () 5. My friends influenced it. ()

11- Do you want to continue postgraduate education?

1)Yes ; If so, in which field are you considering a bachelor's degree?
..... ()
2)No ()

12. How Many Siblings Do You Have?

1) Single () 2) 2 () 3) 3 () 4) 4 () 5) Other.....

13- Which child are you?

1)First () 2) 2nd () 3) 3rd () 4) () 5)

Other.....

14- What are the school and working conditions of your siblings?

1. 1. Child: Studying at
School. Or Working
2. 2. Child: Studying at
School. Or Working
3. 3. Child: Studying at
School. Or Working
4. 4. Child: Studying at
School. Or Working
5. 5. Child: Studying at
School. Or Working

Annex3. Full and Semi- Structured Interview Form Questions

Annex3.1. Fully Structured Interview Form Questions

1. What are your interests outside of school and school?
I like and read type books.
I liketype sports and I do them in
.....
I liketype of music and play
musical instruments.
.....I listen to the lessons with great pleasure at school, I participate
actively and my level of success is high.
I am successful at school in lessons.
Because;.....
.....I like the teacher because of her proactive / active / creative activities in
the lesson. ()
.....I like the teacher because of his explanation and empathetic
approach in the lesson. ()
2. What are your thoughts about your teachers at school? From where?
The fact that the teacher in lessons is young (25-40) is a factor in my
liking the lessons. ()
.....The fact that the teacher in the classes is old (over 40) is a factor in my
liking the lessons. ()

.....I get bored and lose interest in the lesson due to the teacher's proactive/active/creative activities in the lesson. ()

.....My success level in the course is low due to the teacher's direct explanation and cold approach in the course. ()

3. What are your thoughts about the lessons at school? From where?

.....The teacher is a big factor in the fact that I like his classes and increases my success rate. ()

.....My family support is a big factor in my liking my classes and increasing my success rate. ()

.....My individual attention is a big factor in my liking of my classes and increasing my success rate.()

.....My friends are a big factor in my liking my classes and increasing my success rate. ()

.....I don't like your classes and it increases my success rate,..... is a big factor.

4. What are your areas of interest outside of school and school?

➤ I don't liketype books.

➤ I don't like type sports.

➤ I don't like type of music.

➤ I don't like your lessons.

5. What affects your success in classes?

....The separation of my family is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

.....The indifference of my family is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

My family's financial inadequacy is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

The fact that my mother is violent is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

My father's violence is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

My personal indifference is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

My friends are a big factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

.....is a major factor in my dislike of classes and the decrease in my success rate. ()

6. How would you describe yourself? (You can mark more than one.)

- I am a social person. ()
- I am a very social person. ()
- A-I am a social person. ()
- I am at normal level. ()
- I'm bored ()
- I'm so bored ()
- I am excited. ()
- I am very excited ()
- I am active ()
- I am very active ()
- My passive ()
- I am very passive. ()
- I won't let you lose my rights. ()
- I have difficulty defending my rights. ()
- I can represent myself ()
- I am incapable of representing myself. ()
- I can represent the class. ()
- I cannot represent the class. ()
- when a question is asked in class , I immediately raise my hand to answer. ()
- If I know a question is asked in class, I can immediately raise my hand to answer and explain the topic on the board. ()
- Even if I know when a question is asked in class, I prefer not to answer if the teacher does not allow it. ()
- Even if I know when a question is asked in class, if the teacher removes it, I cannot explain the topic on the board. ()
- Even though I know when a question is asked in class, if the teacher removes it, I get very panicked and excited while explaining the topic on the board. ()
- I have self-worth. ()
- My self-worth is low ()
- My self-worth is very low ()

7. Are you interested in politics or policy? What are your thoughts?

- Yes.
Because.....
- No.
Because.....

8. What are your thoughts about the situation of women in social life?

- It should work. ()
- It should not work.()
- should work in social life ,
 - Interest should work for personal preference. ()
 - Must work to support the family (for economic needs). ()
 - It should work in accordance with the social state principle (principle of equality). ()
 - Self-esteem should work for self-worth. ()
 - He should work because his family wants him to. ()
 - Must work for

9. What are your thoughts about women's working life? From where?

- If women should not work in social life;
 - It may work for interest and personal preference. ()
 - His/her family may work because their parents do not want them to ()
 - He can work because his wife prevents him from working ()
 - She can be at home and work to take care of her children. ()
 - Can be at home and work due to household chores . ()
 - In accordance with social ethical rules (women should take care of the housework and children at home, men should bring money to the house). ()
 - It can work for
- If women should work in social life; (you can choose one or several)
 - Can work at a desk ()
 - He can work as a teacher. ()
 - He can work as a doctor. ()
 - Train, Crane etc. Can work as an operator ()
 - Can work as an artist (singer, painter, musician, theater actor, etc.).()
 - Politicians can work as Politicians. ()
 - He can work as an Imam or a teacher. ()
 - He can work as an academic. ()
 - Can work as a tailor, greengrocer, tradesman, dishwasher , etc. ()

- He can work as a journalist. ()
- He can work as a Bus-Minibus Driver. ()
- He can work as a truck driver. ()
- He can work as the owner of a hotel, workplace, newspaper, teaching institution , market or cafe . ()
- Can work as CIO (senior manager in companies). ()
- He can work as an accountant. ()
- He can work as an electrician or real estate agent. ()
- Can work as an engineer (Electrical engineer, Civil engineer, etc.) ()
- He can work as a Minister, Speaker of the Parliament, Minister of Internal Affairs, Minister of Education ()
- Can work as Prime Minister ()
- He can work as President. ()
- Athlete, Athlete, Swimmer, Licensed can work in sports branches ()
- artificial intelligence engineering, Robotics Engineering, Drone Pilot etc. ()
- Can work as a Pilot, Ship Captain, Soldier , General, General, etc. ()
- It should not work.()

10. What are your thoughts about women being managers in Turkey? Why? (Manager, CIO, President, Prime Minister, etc.), in political professions;

- If women are not successful in Management, Press and Politics professions in Turkey;
 - They are not successful due to social judgments. ()
 - They are not successful due to their household responsibilities (housework, etc.). ()
 - They are not successful due to their responsibility for children. ()
 - They are not successful because they did not receive education. ()
 - They are not successful due to lack of self-confidence / self-worth.
 - They are not successful due to social phobia (inability to express in public, inability to speak, excitement, etc.).()
 - They are not successful because their family, spouse-mother-father-sibling-brother do not support or oppose them.()
 - They are not successful because it is a profession that does not have sufficient recognition in Turkey. ()
 - They are not successful because there is no equality between men and women. ()
 - Politics is a suitable profession for men. ()
 - They are successful. ()

11. Are women successful in politics in Türkiye? From where?

- They are successful.Example female politician:
.....
- They fail. Example Female politician:
.....

Annex3.2. Semi-Structured Interview Form Questions

Dear participants,

This research was conducted by the University of St. It is being conducted within the scope of Clements University Psychology Department Undergraduate Thesis and your answers to the questions will be used only for this research. You do not need to write your name and surname. There is no right or wrong answer to any question.

In order to contribute to scientific research, it is extremely important that you answer the questions sincerely and sincerely and do not leave any questions blank. I kindly request you to fill in the () sections of the personal information form below and mark (x) where you see any gaps.

Thank you in advance for your contribution to the research.

Within the scope of the study, answers are sought to the following problem statements:

1. a. Do the effects of demographic characteristics on Social Anxiety differ for adolescents (according to gender, income level, education level, age status, parental culture/marriage bond, age/education, high school type and regional differences)? How?
adolescents , does it create a difference in their views on women's representations regarding career choice tendencies according to gender, income level, regional differences, school type? How?
2. Does the level of Social Anxiety differ according to Social Relationship and Performance, which are the sub-dimensions of demographic characteristics for adolescents (gender, income level, education level, regional difference, age status, parental culture/marriage bond, age/education, school type status)? From where?
3. What are the opinions of senior high school students regarding the political representation of women in Turkey? How?
4. Is there a relationship between women's political representation and social phobia among female and male high school senior students? How?
5. a. Do the attitudes of male and female high school senior students towards women's managerial representations and their intentions for political representations differ significantly? How? From where?
b. Do women's attitudes towards political representation and, in the context of women's managerial tendencies, significantly predict their intentions ? How?
6. If you were to compare the concept of "women's management representation" in Turkey to something, what would you compare it to? From where?

E k4. Liebowitz Social Phobia Scale

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

"None or very mild", "Mild", "Moderate", "Severe", "Sometimes I avoid", "Mostly avoid", "Always avoid" with a sign (x).

Please do not leave any questions unanswered.

	ANXIETY	None or very light	Light	moderately	Severe		AVOIDANCE	None or very light	I avoid it from time to time	I mostly avoid	I Always Avoid
one	Standing up and speaking at a meeting without prior preparation.					one	Standing up and speaking in a meeting without prior preparation				
2	To perform an act, demonstration or speech in front of an audience.					2	To perform an act, demonstration or speech in front of an audience.				
3	To attract attention.					3	To attract attention.				
4	Trying to meet someone with the aim of establishing a romantic relationship.					4	Trying to meet someone with the aim of establishing a romantic relationship.				
5	Presenting prepared oral information to a group.					5	Presenting prepared oral information to a group.				

6	Entering a room while others are inside.					6	Entering a room while others are inside.				
7	Talking to someone more competent than himself					7	Talking to someone more competent than himself				
8	Returning a purchased product to the store to get the money back.					8	Returning a purchased product to the store to get the money back.				
9	Expressing disagreement or displeasure to someone you don't know very well					9	Expressing disagreement or displeasure to someone you don't know very well				
10	Working while being observed					10	Working while being observed				
11	Talking face to face with someone you don't know very well					11	Talking face to face with someone you don't know very well				
12	go to a party					12	go to a party				
13	Looking directly into the eyes of someone you don't know very well					13	Looking directly into the eyes of someone you don't know very well				
14	Testing of ability, skill or knowledge					14	Testing of ability, skill or knowledge				
15	Writing while being observed					15	Writing while being observed				
16	Talking on the phone with someone you don't know very well					16	Talking on the phone with someone you don't know very well				
17	Eating in public places					17	Eating in public places				
18	hosting guests at home					18	hosting guests at home				
19	Participating in a small group activity					19	Participating in a small group activity				
20	Participating in a small group activity					20	Drinking in public places				
21	Using public phones					21	Using public phones				
22	talking to strangers					22	talking to strangers				
23	Resisting intense pressure from salespeople					23	Resisting intense pressure from salespeople				
24	Urinating in a public toilet					24	Urinating in a public toilet				

Appendix 5 . Gender Perception Scale

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

“I completely disagree”,

"I do not agree",

“I am undecided”

"I agree",

"I totally agree"

Please indicate one of the options with an (x). Please do not leave any questions unanswered.

		Totally Disagree	I do not agree	I'm undecided	I agree	I totally agree
one	Marriage does not prevent a woman from working.	()	()	()	()	()
2	A woman should only work if her family has financial difficulties	()	()	()	()	()
3	Working women can also devote enough time to their children.	()	()	()	()	()
4	Women should not work after becoming mothers.	()	()	()	()	()

5	Female politicians can also be successful.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
6	Women should not work after marriage.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
7	Working life does not cause women to neglect their household chores.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
8	A working woman enjoys life more.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
9	Women should always be protected by men.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
10	A woman should not work if her husband does not allow it.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
11th	Women can be managers.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
12	A working woman must give the income she earns to her husband.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
13	A working woman is a better mother to her children.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
14	Men should also do household chores such as laundry and dishes.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
15	A woman without a husband is like an abandoned house.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
16	Men must provide the income for a family.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
17	Women should not open businesses (such as cafes, markets, real estate offices) on their own.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
18	The first duty of women is to undertake housework.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
19	A woman should not earn more money than her husband.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
20	The man should always be the head of the house.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
21	The leadership of society should generally be in the hands of men.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
22	Girls should be given as much freedom as boys.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
23	In order for a woman to have her own rights, she must be able to oppose her husband if necessary.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
24	The woman must be younger than her husband in age.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
25	Men should make important decisions in the family.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

Annex6. Scale UsagePermissions

6.1. Liebowitz Social Phobia Scale Use Permission Approval

Tülin Gençöz
nazmiye eski

22:26
⋮

Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale.docx
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Merhabalar,

Ölçeği bilimsel araştırmalarınızda kullanabilirsiniz. Ölçeği ve makaleyi ekte yolluyorum. "Korku/Anksiyete" ve "Kaçınma" alt-ölçekleri için tüm maddeler ayrı ayrı toplanıyor; ancak bu 2 alt-ölçek korelasyonu yüksek olduğu için ikisinin toplamı "toplam sosyal kaygı" puanı olarak da kullanılabilir.

İyi çalışmalar dileklerle.

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6.2. Gender Perception Scale Use Permission Approval

Re: Toplumsal Cinsiyet Algısı Ölçeği kullanım izni hak

Veli Duyan <duyanveli@yahoo.com>
Kime: Siz

Sayın Nazmiye Eski
Ölçeği çalışmanızda kullanmanızdan memnuniyet duyar başarılar dilerim. Sağlıcakla esenlikle kalın

iPhone'umdan gönderildi

nazmiye eski <nazmiyeeski@hotmail.com> şunları yazdı (18 Oca 2024 16:28):

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